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The spatial design of the ecological remediation of a tailing dam to enhance the dispersal of *Apodemus sylvaticus* and *Carabus violaceus*

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1 University of Bucharest Department of Systems Ecology and Sustainability The spatial design of the ecological remediation of a tailing dam to enhance the dispersal of *Apodemus sylvaticus* and *Carabus violaceus* Student: Coordinators June 2023 Assoc. Professor Virgil Iordache Senior Researcher Florian Bodescu Laryssa Javiera Tarnovschi Cortés 2 Content Chapter Page 1 Introduction 3 2 Literature review 6 2.1 Theoretical principles and modeling of the dispersal of mobile organisms 6 2.1.1 Mapping the literature about the dispersal of mobile organisms 10 2.2 The relationships between ecological connectivity and the production of ecosystem services 16 2.2.1 The topics of biological diversity and ecosystem services in the management of areas with mining and processing industry in their structure 18 3 Site descriptions and Methods 20 3.1 Valea Sesii tailing pond - Study area. 20 3.2 Category of habitats in the remediation scenarios 22 3.3 Model mobile species 23 3.3.1 *Carabus violaceus* 23 3.3.2 *Apodemus sylvaticus* 23 3.4 Spatial analysis and dispersal modeling methodology 25 3.4.1 Spatial analysis 25 3.4.2 Indicator of species presence 25 3.4.3 Agent-based model 26 4 Results and discussions 27 4.1 Spatial design of the ecological remediation 27 4.2 Connectivity between habitats 32 4.3 Use of remediated habitats 39 4.3.1 *Carabus violaceus* 40 4.3.2 *Apodemus sylvaticus* 52 4.4 Connectivity between habitats vs use of remediated habitats 64 5 Conclusion 67 6 References 69 Annexes 73 3 1 Introduction Mining and processing of metalliferous minerals are important causes of ecological deterioration in many catchments, especially in their mountain parts, but also downstream by the dispersion of pollutants along the rivers. Controlling and reversing the deterioration processes due to the mining and processing industry can be done: 1. at the industrial sources (mines, mining dumps, tailing dumps, smelters, and other industrial sources) 2. by transversal buffers to retain the fluxes of pollutants before they enter the streams 3. by longitudinal buffers along the streams, either natural (floodplains) or in the form of treatment wetlands (usually immediately downstream of other forms of control at the source of pollution). The approach of deterioration control is usually sectoral, namely in the responsibility of mining companies and industry ministry at the source, in the responsibility of soil managers or forest managers for transversal buffer zones on the slope area of the catchments, and under the responsibility of water managers along the streams with their floodplains. There is no integration of all types of control measures, but once the concept of ecosystem services was internalized to some extent in the sectoral policies, there is a potential for such integration. The notion and ecosystem service was more rapidly internalized in soil, forest, and water policies, finally arriving in the field of industrial ecology, with the subfield of management of socioecological systems with industrial mining sites. The mining closure phase was in the past approached, in still is in most cases, in isolation of any landscape context and of the contribution of the restored or remediated sites to the production of ecosystem services by the surrounding landscapes. Now there is growing literature about the mining and processing industry

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resources

on the one hand and the species diversity and ecosystem services on the other hand.

Most of this literature deals with the deteriorating effects of mines and industry on the production of ecosystem services, but there are also a few ideas about how to design the remediation and restoration in mining and processing industry areas to contribute to the overall production of ecosystem services in the landscapes. There is a rather complicated taxonomy of greening methods of tailing dams and mining dumps, but for the purpose of this text, we operationally separate only between restoration (which makes sense when the former natural ecosystem is still existing in some degraded state) and remediation (which can be applied also to new ecosystems such piles of rocks and tailing 4 materials). Remediation can be designed based on simple agricultural principles with a single grass or tree species ("engineering approach") or more complex ecological principles, aiming at accelerating the ecological succession during the remediation process ("ecological approach"). The degradation of the environment due to the influence of anthropogenic factors showed remarkable growth during the period of industrial intensification, from 1965 to 1990. One of the major consequences of this revolution was the creation of historically polluted areas or sites, resulting in an alarming situation and practice that continues to this day. With the facts already demonstrated over the years, the deterioration achieved in the restoration of natural resources or the fragmentation of habitats, became a major concern for the generation of ecosystem services. In the current restoration-making is directly linked to the measures, decisions and needs: upon by the European Union, thus putting considerable pressure

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1 Introduction

Mining and processing of metalliferous minerals are important causes of ecological deterioration in many catchments, especially in their mountain parts, but also downstream by the dispersion of pollutants along the rivers.

Controlling and reversing the deterioration processes due to the mining and processing industry can be done:

1. at the industrial sources (mines, mining dumps, tailing dumps, smelters, and other industrial sources)
2. by transversal buffers to retain the fluxes of pollutants before they enter the streams
3. by longitudinal buffers along the streams, either natural (floodplains) or in the form of treatment wetlands (usually immediately downstream of other forms of control at the source of pollution).

The approach of deterioration control is usually sectoral, namely in the responsibility of mining companies and industry ministry at the source, in the responsibility of soil managers or forest managers for transversal buffer zones on the slope area of the catchments, and under the responsibility of water managers along the streams with their floodplains.

There is no integration of all types of control measures, but once the concept of ecosystem services was internalized to some extent in the sectoral policies, there is a potential for such integration. The notion and ecosystem service was more rapidly internalized in soil, forest, and water policies, finally arriving in the field of industrial ecology, with the subfield of management of socio-ecological systems with industrial mining sites. The mining closure phase was in the past approached, in still is in most cases, in isolation of any landscape context and of the contribution of the restored or remediated sites to the production of ecosystem services by the surrounding landscapes. Now there is growing literature about the mining and processing industry on the one hand and the species diversity and ecosystem services on the other hand. Most of this literature deals with the deteriorating effects of mines and industry on the production of ecosystem services, but there are also a few ideas about how to design the remediation and restoration in mining and processing industry areas to contribute to the overall production of ecosystem services in the landscapes. There is a rather complicated taxonomy of greening methods of tailing dams and mining dumps, but for the purpose of this text, we operationally separate only between restoration (which makes sense when the former natural ecosystem is still existing in some degraded state) and remediation (which can be applied also to new ecosystems such piles of rocks and tailing

materials). Remediation can be designed based on simple agricultural principles with a single grass or tree species (“engineering approach”) or more complex ecological principles, aiming at accelerating the ecological succession during the remediation process (“ecological approach”).

The degradation of the environment due to the influence of anthropogenic factors showed remarkable growth during the period of industrial intensification, from 1965 to 1990. One of the major consequences of this revolution was the creation of historically polluted areas or sites, resulting in an alarming situation and practice that continues to this day. With the facts already demonstrated over the years, the deterioration achieved through the overexploitation of natural resources or the fragmentation of habitats, became an unsustainable practice, for example, for the generation of ecosystem services.

In the current Romanian context, decision-making is directly linked to the measures, decisions and needs established and agreed upon by the European Union, thus putting considerable pressure on the country's legislative powers. It is also worth mentioning that the United Nations Organization has placed emphasis on the sustainable and durable development of various areas of the social, economic, and ecological sectors.

Due to the above, action must be taken, mainly measures focused on the need to test and substantiate scientific methods of rehabilitation and ecological reconstruction at the national level. This need is legislatively supported by the National Strategy and the National Plan for the Management of Contaminated Situations in Romania (HG 683/2015).

The idea of the research project (<https://resetbiogeochemistry.wordpress.com/>) which hosted the research reported in this license thesis is a combination of the two, namely to devise the remediation at two scales, a small patch phytoremediation scale (with plants in combination with symbiotic fungi) and a spatial design of several types of patches (microhabitats) to enhance the dispersal of mobile species from the surrounding ecosystems. The activities of the thesis belong to the second objective of the project, how to spatially design vegetation microhabitats on the surface of the closed tailing dam. It is assumed that an enhanced dispersal of specie on the phyto-stabilized tailing (covered with vegetation that keeps most of the toxic elements in their root system and minimally transfer them aboveground) would lead more rapidly to high species richness in the remediated ecosystems, which in turn would be positively correlated with a higher role of the remediated tailing dam in the production of ecosystem services at the local landscape scale. This

assumption (although itself a matter of research in ecology) is reasonable and generally accepted when evaluating the ecosystem service of maintaining species diversity.

In Romania, in the Apuseni mountains, there are many functioning and closed mining sites and processing sites near Natura 2000 sites and national parks. The largest open pit for copper mining is owned by the Cuprumin S.A. state company, is located near the Arieş river, the Trascău mountain N2000 site, and will be closed in about 20 years. We took the largest tailing dam of Cuprumin S.A., Valea Seşii tailing dam, as a model system because the company was interested in the technology developed in the mentioned project. Remediation technologies develop from readiness level TRL0 (concept) to TRL12 (fully operational), and up to level 4 (demonstration) they are usually developed by public research organizations with public funds to catalyze their later uptake by industrial actors for further development from level 5 (transfer) to 12. The activities of this license contribute to the development between TRL4 and 5 levels.

In this context, **the goal** of the license is to contribute to the development of a TRL4 eco-remediation technology of tailing dams, and **the objectives** are:

- to screen the literature relevant to the dispersal of mobile organisms on remediated tailing dams
- to simulate the dispersal of two selected species in different scenarios of spatial design of the vegetation microhabitats on the tailing dam.

2 Literature review

2.1 Theoretical principles and modeling of the dispersal of mobile organisms

The dispersal of mobile organisms is modeled differently depending on the organisms, sometimes on the age class, and the abiotic pathway (water, air, terrestrial). For the purpose of this thesis, we look for the dispersal of epigeous terrestrial invertebrates, small rodents, amphibians, and reptiles because, according to the published literature, their dispersal is controlled by the spatial pattern of microhabitats in remediated mining areas (Iordache 2020). The dispersal of large mammals and birds depends mostly on the landscape structure at a large scale and is not controlled by the state of the remediated ecosystem, while the dispersal of soil invertebrates with very small mobility is controlled mostly by stochastic processes and development of soil/organic matter accumulation in the remediated ecosystem, which is a long-term process and cannot be manipulated very much by design, only accelerated by the phytostabilization method at microhabitat scale.

By dispersal I operationally mean here the movement of organisms from the space/habitat where there is a population to a habitat located nearby and not having such a population. I am aware that depending on the conceptualization of the movement of organisms, one can have much finer distinctions between categories of movement (e.g., figure 1). For instance, in the case of simulating the colonization of the microhabitats of a tailing dam, one cannot distinguish between dispersal as supporting gene flow and nomadism (movement between transient areas where individuals of a population are located). Such details depend on future research on the actual populations developed after the colonization processes.

The most common approaches to modeling dispersal in landscape ecology are the least-cost models and individual-based dispersal models (IBDMs) (Diniz et al. 2020). The models based on raster representations of the landscape use the concept of resistance surface, which results from the resistance to the movement of the organisms provided by each discretization unit (raster unit) in the landscape (figure 2). Table 1 summarizes how various aspects of dispersal can be incorporated in dispersal models based on landscape connectivity.

If one focuses on IBDMs, one can see that they can be classified in function of their relevance to decision-making and the complexity they account for (figure 3). Current IBDMs can simulate thousands of individuals in realistic environments and with highly detailed internal physiology, perception and ability to process the perceptions and make decisions based on those and their

internal states (DeAngelis and Diaz 2019). The implementation of decision-making in IBDMs ranges from fairly simple to highly complex; the process of an individual deciding on an action can occur through the use of logical and simple (if-then) rules to more sophisticated neural networks and genetic algorithms (DeAngelis and Diaz 2019).

Movement type & long-term pattern	Characteristic features and function	Spatial scale of community effect
<p>Dispersal</p>	<p><i>Movement leading to gene flow. Typically, this is movement between natal and reproductive site (natal dispersal; once per lifetime) or between sites of reproduction (sometimes referred to as breeding dispersal; possibly multiple times per lifetime).</i></p> <p>Dispersal is an important mechanism for maintaining genetic diversity, both for actively and passively moving organisms. Passively dispersing organisms often have a specific life-cycle stage (e.g. spore, egg, seed) that is adapted to being transported by abiotic vectors (e.g. wind or water) or biotic vectors (genetic mobile links).</p>	<p>Direct effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional • Interregional
<p>Migration</p>	<p><i>Bi-directional movements between distinct breeding and non-breeding sites, which are often long distance in relation to body size.</i></p> <p>Migrating animals use seasonally variable resources or escape seasonal risks (seasonal migration; one to multiple times per lifetime), or complete their life cycle in different habitats, e.g. aquatic and terrestrial (life-cycle migration; once per lifetime). Outside the actual migratory phase, individuals may perform station-keeping or nomadic movement within their breeding and non-breeding range.</p>	<p>Direct effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional • Interregional <p>Mobile-link effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional • Interregional
<p>Station-keeping movement</p>	<p><i>Daily movements within a restricted area (home range).</i></p> <p>Range-resident animals perform station-keeping movements throughout their lifetime, possibly excepting dispersal phases. Although home ranges can be dynamic in space and time, they are typically used throughout the reproductive lifetime of an individual. We also refer to station-keeping movements when migratory animals perform their daily movements such as foraging outside the migratory phase in restricted areas.</p>	<p>Direct effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local <p>Mobile-link effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional
<p>Nomadism</p>	<p><i>Undirected movements between irregularly shifting transient core areas (multiple times within months, a year, or a lifetime).</i></p> <p>Nomadic animals typically use resources that change irregularly in space and time. Nomadic movements between transient core areas are interspersed with daily local movements. In this way, some nomadic animals cover large distances during their lifetime. Nomadism may also occur seasonally, e.g. only during the non-breeding season. Nomadism differs from dispersal, as nomadic movements occur typically within a population rather than a metapopulation (see also Mueller & Fagan, 2008).</p>	<p>Direct effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local • Regional <p>Mobile-link effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional

Figure 1 Types of movement in the conceptualization of Schlagel et al. (2020).

Figure 2 Landscape resistance to animal movement and the framework of connectivity models. A resistance surface represents the differential propensity of an organism to use a particular habitat type (a). Least-cost models convert the resistance surface into a weighted-graph network in which nodes (cells' centroids) are connected by weighted edges according to the Euclidean distance and resistance values from the neighboring cells (b). In the circuit theory-based model, the edges are replaced by resistors (c). Using an IBDM, it is possible to incorporate behavioral elements that drive individuals' movement (d) (figure and legend from Diniz et al. 2020).

Figure 3 Schematic representation of the models and methodologies utilized to model decision-making in ecology (figure and legend from DeAngelis and Diaz 2019).

Table 1 The importance of some aspects of animal dispersal and how they have been incorporated into connectivity modeling (table and legend from Diniz et al. 2020).

Dispersal aspect	Importance	Possible approach
Resistance to dispersal	It must reflect the pattern of habitat use during dispersal	It can be captured using direct dispersal data to produce the resistance surface. Proxies such as home-range movement data can be used for some species
Seasonality	Systems with pronounced seasonal spatial variation in forage and water availability or when the species exhibits differences in habitat preferences between seasons	Produce seasonal resistance surfaces
Animal perception	How an organism perceives the landscape around it and makes its decisions will have strong effect on its movement pattern	Different perceptions can be represented by different connectivity models. Exploratory movements and other dispersal behaviors may help define the most appropriate model. Complex behavior can be better modeled using an IBDM
Perceptual range	It is important to consider in connectivity analyses made in high resolution and where the cell's size does not match with the radius of target species' perception	Some LC models and IBDMs are able to explicitly incorporate this feature. A multi-scale model of landscape resistance can consider the specific scale with which environmental variables can affect movement
Mortality during dispersal	Neglecting mortality may overestimate successful dispersal and compromise the effectiveness of corridors	It can be inserted indirectly via resistance surface or modeled through IBDMs and CT (although in a not very trivial way in the latter)
Individual variability	Heterogeneity in dispersal among individuals may arise as a consequence of differences between sex, physiological condition, and personalities	It is possible to incorporate via resistance surface and modifying some models' parameters such as dispersal distance
Time	Patch connectivity may depend on time	Only IBDMs can incorporate a time framework for connectivity

Space use theories tend to be developed specifically for various groups of organisms, but the theoretical framework relevant for one group can provide hints to experts specialized in other groups. An example is the work of Young and Shivik (2006) “What carnivore biologists can learn from bugs, birds, and beavers: a review of spatial theories”. This is an important aspect, because from the perspective of landscape ecology spatial modelers and of the theoretical biologists (Broom et al. 2020) the approaches tend to be presented as having universal relevance. When it comes to calibrating and validating the models, besides scenarios development, one would need a tight cooperation between landscape ecologists/theoretical biologists and the experts in the groups of organisms.

2.1.1 Mapping the literature about the dispersal of mobile organisms

In English the Romanian word “dispersie” translates either in “dispersion”, which in the environmental science literature and ecology is used in the context of pollutants dispersion by abiotic fluxes (air, water), or in the word “dispersal”, which refers to active or passive dispersal of organisms.

In order to map the literature about modeling the dispersal of selected groups of organisms I have searched in Web of Science (option “topic”) for X_AND_dispersal_AND_modelling, and then downloaded from the citation report the set of articles citing the core articles, where X was:

- Beetles (time span 1991-2023), Amphibian (2006-2023), Rodent (2000-2023), Frog (2006-2023), Ant (2002-2023), Snake (2012-2023), Small mammal (2003-2023), Reptile (2010-2023)

The groups of organisms were those whose dispersal depends on the spatial structure of microhabitats of a remediated mining dump/tailing dam. An example of the search interface is in figure 4a.

Figure 4a Example of Web of Science interface after searching for frog AND dispersal AND modeling, and downloading the bibliometric information of citing articles from the citation report. The number of core articles found is 290, and the extended set is 9124 in this case.

I downloaded the bibliometric information of the core articles and of the extended set of citing articles in each search and mapped the clusters of knowledge with the software Citespace following the procedure described in Appendix 1 of this thesis. In the first version of the analysis, I united all the core articles found in Web of Science and attempted to map the citations in between for all groups of organisms. There was no grouping of articles by citations between the articles dealing with different groups of organisms, which proved that the dispersal modeling of the organisms belongs to separate lines of research. In the second version I mapped the extended set of articles resulted from each separate search. In figure 4b and 4c one can find examples of results for the case of small mammals, and in table 2 the description of the clusters. Other examples are in Appendix 2 of this thesis (for beetles, amphibians and reptiles).

The inspection of the cluster of literature has shown that:

- For beetles there are three clusters (1, 10 and 14, average year of publication 2019, 2013, 2014) including the keyword ecosystem service.
- For amphibians there is a single cluster (5, average year of publication 2019) including the keyword ecosystem service.
- For the other groups of organisms modeling the dispersal was not yet intensively related to the problem of ecosystem service, such as generating clusters of literature.
- For amphibians there is a cluster (2, average year of publication 2020) including the keyword surface mine, and dealing with the toxicity of ponds formed in closed surface mines on amphibians dispersed in such habitats.
- For the other groups of organisms there are no clusters including the keywords mining, surface mine, smelter, tailing, dump, or industry.

I infer from this analysis that the problem of dispersal of organisms to remediated tailing dams in relation to the production of ecosystem service of the integrating landscape has not been approached by many scientists in the past. This points out the novelty of the second objective of this thesis.

The preliminary results of mapping the literature in Citespace can eventually be upgraded in a systematic review of the topic by cooperation with experts in each group of target organisms, namely those involved in the research project dealing with eco-remediation technology.

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 WoS: D:\LITERATURE\AND_dispersal_AND_modelling\Small-mammal_AND_dispersal_AND_modelling\DATE_FILTERATE
 Timespan: 2003-2023 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: Top 50 per slice, LRF=3.0, L/N=10, LBY=5, e=1.0
 Network: N=830, E=3885 (Density=0.0113)
 Largest CC: 754 (90%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.7163
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.8774
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.7887

Figure 4b Clusters of literature in the extended set for the search of small mammal AND dispersal and modeling.

Figure 4b continuation. Time line of the same clusters.

Table 2 Cluster description corresponding to the extended set of articles for the search of small mammal AND dispersal and modeling.

ClusterID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSI)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	122	0.871	2015	habitat amount; fragmented landscape; small mammal; habitat amount hypothesis; habitat fragmentation landscape connectivity; landscape pattern; road effect; temporal variation; genomic variation	habitat amount hypothesis (2606.63, 1.0E-4); habitat amount (2290.04, 1.0E-4); seed dispersal (2239.4, 1.0E-4); small mammal (1592.16, 1.0E-4); patch size (1205.01, 1.0E-4)	metacommunity structure (5.94); sex-specific corre
1	83	0.851	2008	brazilian atlantic forest; atlantic forest; fragmented landscape; forest fragmentation; critical threshold fragmented habitat; fungal attack; little effect; developing seed; structured decision	critical threshold (972.29, 1.0E-4); occupancy dynamics (932.49, 1.0E-4); fragment size (856.6, 1.0E-4); species characteristics (842.39, 1.0E-4); atlantic forest landscape (804.46, 1.0E-4)	metacommunity structure (0.84); sex-specific corre
2	83	0.919	2000	fragmented landscape; spatial ecology; matrix heterogeneity; individual behavior; patchy landscape habitat fragmentation; agricultural landscape; population dynamics; forestry plantation establishment; diffusion processes	spatial ecology (783.23, 1.0E-4); individual behavior (761.99, 1.0E-4); patchy landscape (712.5, 1.0E-4); habitat corridor (684.21, 1.0E-4); matrix heterogeneity (623.61, 1.0E-4)	metacommunity structure (0.23); sex-specific corre
3	78	0.797	2008	landscape connectivity; functional connectivity; fragmented landscape; rethinking landscape metrics; landscape ecology graph-based approach; linear infrastructure; ecological assessment; landscape approach; handling multiple ecological requirement	landscape connectivity (658.47, 1.0E-4); rethinking landscape metrics (417.25, 1.0E-4); genetic studies (409.65, 1.0E-4); patch-based graph (402.06, 1.0E-4); protected forest area network (394.44, 1.0E-4)	metacommunity structure (0.17); sex-specific corre
4	73	0.865	2013	cryptic diversity; genetic structure; evolutionary history; integrative taxonomy; new species south america; multilocus phylogeny; afrotropical long-fingered bat; cryptic radiation; conservation genomics	cryptic diversity (1237.34, 1.0E-4); evolutionary history (1034.9, 1.0E-4); integrative taxonomy (942.18, 1.0E-4); new species (921.1, 1.0E-4); recent population expansion (908.46, 1.0E-4)	metacommunity structure (1.12); sex-specific corre
5	71	0.87	2001	fragmented landscape; habitat fragmentation; extinction threshold; oregon coast range; landscape heterogeneity heterogeneous landscape; habitat loss; landscape ecology; host-parasite dynamics; matrix habitat	heterogeneous landscape (973.34, 1.0E-4); oregon coast range (911.05, 1.0E-4); extinction threshold (855.34, 1.0E-4); confounding factor (467.08, 1.0E-4); landscape-level pattern (460.95, 1.0E-4)	metacommunity structure (0.35); sex-specific corre
6	65	0.797	2004	small mammal; diffusion model; case study; larch plantation matrix; landscape connectivity american marten; genetic isolation; nonspatial parameter; using grip; population viability	diffusion model (525.91, 1.0E-4); larch plantation matrix (486, 1.0E-4); using randomization procedure (423.01, 1.0E-4); spatial distribution pattern (420.4, 1.0E-4); novel environment (409.56, 1.0E-4)	metacommunity structure (0.35); sex-specific corre
7	44	0.982	2018	case study; ecological security pattern; ecological network; mountainous area; guangdong-hong kong-macao landscape connectivity; combining spatial modeling tool; multispecies assessment; ecological restoration; restoration area	ecological security pattern (3906.23, 1.0E-4); case study (2269.97, 1.0E-4); ecological network (1499.16, 1.0E-4); mountainous area (792.76, 1.0E-4); guangdong-hong kong-macao (618.55, 1.0E-4)	defining corridor (0.24); multiple species (0.24);

8	42	0.869	2009	natal dispersal; landscape connectivity; great tit; local density; polygynous mammal population density; population dynamics; density-dependent dispersal; ecological network; dispersal syndrome	natal dispersal (678, 1.0E-4); population density (655.56, 1.0E-4); individual dispersal landscape connectivity (445.49, 1.0E-4); great tit (441.74, 1.0E-4); density-dependent dispersal (417.09, 1.0E-4)	sex-specific correlation (0.2); metacommunity stru
9	39	0.952	2004	genetic structure; habitat fragmentation; south-eastern australia; fine-scale genetic structure; local genetic structure host habitat patchiness; distance decay; gastro-intestinal nematode communities; passer domesticus; high connectivity	south-eastern australia (635.42, 1.0E-4); fine-scale genetic structure (579.08, 1.0E-4); local genetic structure (522.93, 1.0E-4); landscape barrier (428.77, 1.0E-4); underlying life histories (423.26, 1.0E-4)	low male (0.21); female-biased dispersal (0.21); m
10	28	0.961	2012	american pika; mainland region; habitat area; isolated region; water balance low-elevation pika; plastic pika; behavioural flexibility; behavioral ecology; eastern california	american pika (3351.5, 1.0E-4); mainland region (378.32, 1.0E-4); isolated region (378.32, 1.0E-4); water balance (378.32, 1.0E-4); interior range margin (369.71, 1.0E-4)	mediterranean population (0.09); tuber melanosporu
12	13	0.986	2007	relative contribution; species composition; host composition; deconstructing spatial pattern; ectoparasite communities desert rodent; comparative ecology; genetic differentiation; matrix resistance; complex landscape	environmental variable (184.44, 1.0E-4); host composition (184.44, 1.0E-4); deconstructing spatial pattern (184.44, 1.0E-4); relative contribution (184.44, 1.0E-4); species composition (184.44, 1.0E-4)	fragmented landscape (0.01); range expansion (0.01)
13	13	0.997	2010	vertebrate fauna; tropical savanna woodland; livestock grazing; grazing management; tropical savanna terrestrial mammal abundance; conservation land tenure; north-eastern australian tropical savanna; invasive bank vole; ongoing range expansion	vertebrate fauna (451.17, 1.0E-4); tropical savanna woodland (162.89, 1.0E-4); livestock grazing (162.89, 1.0E-4); grazing management (149.27, 1.0E-4); temporal effect (149.27, 1.0E-4)	fragmented landscape (0.01); habitat amount (0.01)

2.2 The relationships between ecological connectivity and the production of ecosystem services

A general scheme linking landscape connectivity and ecosystem service provision is provided by Mitchell et al. (2013, figure 5). These authors also provide a review and propose research directions about the influence of connectivity. In a later opinion article, Mitchell et al. (2015) further elaborated the conceptual diagram of the effects of landscape fragmentation on ecosystem services production and separated the effect on ecosystem services supply from those on flow as positive externalities.

Figure 5 Landscape connectivity can directly affect ecosystem service provision by influencing the magnitude of movement of organisms and matter (black arrows), and indirectly influencing the biodiversity and ecosystem functions that the landscape contains (gray arrows). Human activities influence landscape structure by changing land cover and land use (dashed gray arrows) (figure and legend from Mitchell et al. 2013).

The positive externalities are due to the large scale of production and the heterogeneity of distribution of production processes inside landscapes, allowing a spatial separation of source areas and mostly benefiting areas (Dolan et al. 2021, Cui et al. 2022, figure 6). One can notice also the presence of negative externalities in some cases because the value of ecological, species-specific connectivity in landscapes depends on the ecosystem services or disservices provided by the species (Egerer and Anderson 2020). The connectivity of social-ecological systems promotes also resilience across landscapes to the stress factors (Egerer et al. 2020b). Depending on the mobile species using the landscape connectivity one can also have tradeoffs between the ecosystem services provided at the landscape scale (figure 7).

Wang et al. (2021) use the notion of resistance surface (chapter 1.1 in this license) to model the effects of mobile species dispersal on the landscape scale ecosystem services. In a different approach, Zhang et al. (2022) correlate various indices of landscape structure with the provision of ecosystem services.

1. Four types of ecosystem service flows

2. Natural-social coupled system

3. Overall ecological safety network

Figure 6 Examples of spatial relationships between areas producing ecosystem services and areas benefiting from the positive externalities (from Cui et al. 2022).

Figure 7 Conceptual framework illustrating how herbivory acts as a mechanism through which landscape connectivity affects ecosystem service provision. The diagram illustrates the types of relationships (arrows) between connectivity, insect herbivory, and ecosystem services. Connectivity can either maintain populations of non-outbreak species, or reduce the extent and duration of outbreaks (positively affecting ecosystem services), or facilitate outbreaks (negatively affecting ecosystem services). (figure and legend from Maguire et al. (2015).

2.2.1 The topics of biological diversity and ecosystem services in the management of areas with mining and processing industry in their structure

Neagoe (coordinator, 2022) mapped the scientific literature using the keywords presented in table 3 and the software Citespace and obtained the clusters of scientific knowledge represented in figure 8. One can notice that the research is mediated by methodological approaches (e.g., critical metal concentration, bioconcentration factor, lead isotopes, tree ring mercury records), by case studies, usually ecological systems with large mining disasters (e.g., the Doce river in Brazil), and that there is a new cluster dealing with the spatial variation problem, reflecting the extensive use of spatial analysis, including the landscape connectivity effects.

Table 3 Keywords and syntax used for mapping the literature about several types of ecosystems, rehabilitation/restoration, ecosystem services, biodiversity, and two sources of pollution in mining and processing industry areas (Neagoe coordinator 2022).

Forest	AND	smelter	Forest	AND	"tailing dam"
Grassland	AND	smelter	Grassland	AND	"tailing dam"
Floodplain	AND	smelter	Floodplain	AND	"tailing dam"
Wetland	AND	smelter	Wetland	AND	"tailing dam"
Rehabilitation	AND	smelter	Rehabilitation	AND	"tailing dam"
Restoration	AND	smelter	Restoration	AND	"tailing dam"
ecosystem services	AND	smelter	ecosystem services	AND	"tailing dam"
biodiversity	AND	smelter	biodiversity	AND	"tailing dam"

Inside this large body of literature, there is an increasing presence of explicit approaches to ecosystem services. Ribeiro et al. (2018) proposes a rehabilitation of a manganese tailing dam to increase plant taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional diversity, aiming at the effect of this diversity on the production of ecosystem services. Martins et al (2020) make a review of ecological methods and indicators for recovering the functions and services and monitoring ecosystems after mining. Lima et al. (2020) take into account the ecosystem services lost due to a tailing dam disaster in Brazil. This kind of approach is very important when the mining areas and industry are spotted in biodiversity-rich landscapes (Kamino et al. 2020). Souza et al (2021) list a set of mitigation measures to compensate for the decrease in ecosystem services production due to mines including landscape scale spatial planning. Besides theoretical considerations, it is proved that the proximity of certain ecosystem types, such as forests, to the remediated mining areas contributed to the success of the remediation measures (Konig et al. 2022). In 2023 one already has examples of remediation technologies aiming an improving of ecosystem services delivery by catchments affected by mining activities (Bonnail et al. 2023).

CiteSpace, v. 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced
 July 27, 2022 at 2:55:29 PM EEST
 WoS: C:\Users\Virgil Iordache\citespace\Examples\WoS\SmelterTailingRemedRestorES\Data_Filtered_2_cu_BDV
 Timespan: 1975-2023 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: g-index (k=25), LRF=3.0, L/N=10, LBY=5, e=1.0
 Network: N=2670, E=10431 (Density=0.0029)
 Largest CC: 2142 (80%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.8973
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.952
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.9238

Figure 8 The main clusters of knowledge correspond to the keywords and syntax from table 4. The oldest articles are on the left (1997), and the newest on the right (September 2022) (from Neagoe coordinator 2022).

3 Site descriptions and Methods

3.1 Valea Şesii tailing pond - Study area.

To contextualize, the creation and use of this tailing pond was due to the industrial process of anthropic mining activity in the area, which was developed in the Apuseni mountains network, in the commune of Lupşa, in the Şesii Valley.

The activity of exploitation and extraction of the material mineral resource, copper metal, was carried out in the mine called Roşia Poieni (located at point B, represented with the shape of yellow polygon, in figure 9), where, in addition to obtaining this raw material by means of the respective technical process and all the stages involved, a remaining metallurgical concentrate is also produced as a result of this activity (Lazăr and Faur 2013).

This concentrate of metallurgical wastes which is the product of a physical operational stage, called the selective flotation process, is transported from the Dealul Piciorului treatment plant (located at point C, represented by the orange polygon shape, in figure 1) in a hydraulically and gravitationally manner to the tailing pond of Şesei Valley (located at point A, represented by the light blue polygon shape, in figure 1) where these wastes are deposited, accumulated and sedimented (Lazăr and Faur 2013).

Figure 9 Graphical representation of – Point A: Şesii Valley, tailing dam, represented by the light blue polygon – Point B: Mine Roşia Poieni, represented with the shape of yellow polygon – Point C: Dealul Piciorului treatment plant, represented by the orange polygon shape.

According to Lazăr and Faur (2013), the risk assessment methodology provided by Ministry Order no. 184/1997 (approving the procedure for environmental assessments) issued by the Romanian government, can conclude that the waste dams or ponds studied present a moderate risk to the environment. They also mention that due to the activities that take place at the processing plant, Dealul Piciorului, there is a great potential for impact (effects) on the flora, fauna, and water surfaces of the environment, caused mainly by the water consumption, wastewater discharges, emissions of macro pollutants and land occupation (Lazăr and Faur 2013).

The total selected surface of the tailings pond (represented by point A in Figure 9) was not used in its entirety for the realization of this project, where from this a partial selection of the desired area was made, being called the study area (represented by Figure 10). This study zone is also part of the area of interest (represented by Figure 11), where an external portion was added to the settling pond, taking into consideration the habitats bordering it.

Figure 10 Graphical representation of the area corresponding to the study zone.

Figure 11 Graphical representation of the area of interest, which includes the study area.

3.2 Category of habitats in the remediation scenarios

The TRL 4 Remediation Eco-technology of tailing dams uses four categories of remediated habitats (figure 12), of which we focus in this study only on spatial structure of two types of habitats: pastures and forests. We selected these habitats because in the final remediated state of the tailing dam they cover most of the surface.

Figure 12 Potential general distribution of habitat categories on the remediated tailing dam (blue – pond, green – wetland, light green – pastures, and yellow – forests) (from Neagoe coordinator 2022)

3.3 Model mobile species

3.3.1 *Carabus violaceus*

The ground beetle identified as *Carabus violaceus*, which belongs to the order Coleoptera and family Carabidae (Bîrzanu and Mitrea 2021), is used as a first order consumer in our project. This invertebrate has a body length of ≥ 20 mm, with a brachypterous anatomical disposition, with a "pusher" type of locomotion, and is considered a generalist predator (Bargmann 2016). Regarding to the seasonal breeding period, these individuals are autumn breeders (Bargmann 2016) and during the hibernation period, this species hibernates in the form of larvae, due to this strategy, this beetle presents its greatest moment of manifestation and activity in the summer months (Šiška, et. al. 2020. Bargmann 2016).

In terms of habitat preference, these species are present in wet grasslands, being less common in grasslands rich in dry dead vegetation (Hatteland 2005). They can also be found in May, June and September in previously grazed clover-grass pastures (Beye et. al. 2023). It is also considered a species that has an affinity for forest-type habitats, being an eurytopic forest species, which translates as a species that possesses the ability to live in a wide variety of ecosystems of one habitat type and to tolerate variable intervals of parameters, with respect to forest habitats. (Hatteland 2005). Being general forest dwellers, they can be found in different forest compositions, such as poplar, oak, birch, and black acacia forests (Gyözö and Csaba 2005) without showing a preference for humidity (Bargmann 2016).

The dispersal of the flightless ground beetle must be considered from the point of view that these individuals do not present a specific habitat preference, where it has to be evaluated in different zones, with different parameters. With respect to the results provided by Elek, et. al., (2014), the conclusions on the data were divided into 50 m classes in terms of covered distances (m), where it was demonstrated that the first two classes (the 1-50 m (class 1) and 50-100 m (class 2)) were dominant in the three habitats where the studies were conducted.

3.3.2 *Apodemus sylvaticus*

This species is also identified by the common name of long-tailed field mouse, which according to The Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS), is taxonomically classified as follows: Kingdom: Animalia, Phylum: Chordata, Subphylum: Vertebrata, Class: Mammalia (Linnaeus, 1758), Order: Rodentia (Bowdich 1821), Family: Muridae (Illiger 1811), Genus: *Apodemus* (Kaup, 1829), Species: *Apodemus sylvaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

The habitat preference of this species is related to the quality of the plots, where there is an interest in agricultural plots and forests habitats (Díaz and Morán-López 2023). In addition, one of the influencing factors is the availability of food in the respective habitats, which affects the population dynamics of this common field mouse across forest landscapes (Díaz and Morán-López 2023)

These rodents use their ability to extract available food resources in the spring and summer seasons and then retreat to the forests after harvesting (Díaz and Morán-López 2023). Where during the autumn and winter seasons they inhabit forest plots where they benefit from food resources, for example, the acorn production from oak trees and food resources available in nearby plots (example: seeds from harvested crops) (Díaz and Morán-López 2023).

With respect to the above mentioned, it can be justified and explained that the greatest reproductive activity takes place in small fragments and forest edges during the fall (Díaz and Morán-López 2023). It is also suggested that the reproductive cycle in northern and central Europe starts in early spring and ends in late summer or early autumn (Massoud et. al. 2021).

Due to the seasonal periods of reproduction and hibernation, there are consequences such as migration type movements. This integrates and utilizes one of the most important qualities of the species, which is the spatial dispersion or home range interval. With respect to this small mammal, it represented a minimum of 104.3 m of distance traveled in 1 month, which is equivalent to 1,252 m in the time scale of one year. (Dickman and Doncaster 1989).

With respect to the population density parameter of this species, reference is made to the dependence of density on the last part of the reproductive period (Montgomery 1989). As evidenced by Bobek (1971) with respect to the population density of *Apodemus sylvaticus* in a forest type habitat with the presence of oak and hornbeam, he obtained a result with a mean value of 17 individuals of the species per hectare, where it also obtained the values of 856 and 535 kcal/ha per year in terms of biomass accumulation.

Table 4 summary of the material data used for the project modeling.

	Habitat preference	Home range (per day)	Breeding season
<i>Carabus violaceus</i>	Pastures	50 m	Autumn
<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>	Forest	200 m	Autumn

3.4 Spatial analysis and dispersal modeling methodology

3.4.1 Spatial analysis

For the spatial analysis and the graphical representation, we used the instrument called Geographic Information System (QGIS).

This methodology was carried out in a structural and hierarchical way, where the steps were performed in chronological order and directly related to the use of the theoretically extracted data with respect to the chosen materials. QGIS was used as the instrument for the integration of the datasets in relation to the main idea for carrying out this project.

For the creation of an optimal spatial unit, it was necessary to use different tools and processes, such as the generation of vector layers with different shapes, data selection and filtering, the creation and adaptation of graphical models and the merging of information and models with other types of instruments, for example, Google Earth pro and Repast Symphony.

3.4.2 Indicator of species presence

With the approach of this methodology, we had to use the instrument called Maxent. This is a software tool based on the modeling of the maximum entropy of geographical distributions of species, which uses different index variables that can influence this spatial distribution, such as climatic variation with respect to precipitation, the geomorphological element of elevation and also the potential use of vegetation layers in different scenarios, in terms of the presence of habitats (Phillips 2005).

This instrument was mainly used to corroborate the presence or absence of *Carabus violaceus* and *Apodemus sylvaticus*, in the different habitats located in the study area. It is important to mention that this program does not operate with a temporal scale, but only takes into consideration the classification of the variables mentioned above.

We proposed the use of the respective method of calculating the maximum entropy, this instrument called Maxent was considered as a guide method, but at the time of making the calculations, the spatial scale was considered too small to obtain results, where the lack of data regarding the parameters of the state of the ecosystem were not sufficient for the development of the model in the Maxent instrument, which should be applied in the extensive regional scale, where you can see the difference of other parameters of the state of the ecosystem (temperature, humidity, etc.), but the data obtained at present do not make a very accentuated discrepancy.) but the data obtained at present do not make a very accentuated discrepancy. The maxent instrument was not used because it does not fit the time of analysis nor the spatial scale point of view.

3.4.3 Agent-based model

This methodology is based on simulations, which are created from agents. These agents are assigned attributes (characteristic elements) such as the representation of the objective/intention to achieve, the representation of the actions that can be performed and the representation of the environment (Wooldridge 2002).

Due to the presence of multi-agents with their specific non-linear behaviors, which act with a name (may have arguments), a precondition list (a set of facts that must be fulfilled prior to the action), an elimination list (facts that are no longer true after executing the action) and an addition list (facts that become true when executing the action). It is worth mentioning that each of these lists may contain variables (Wooldridge 2002).

The use of this type of model is to evaluate the behavior and distribution of each individual in the population in terms of spatial utilization, where interactions produce effects. These effects can be translated as the deliberation of an agent, where a part of this project was based on the functional component called as the generation of options, where the agent generates a set of possible alternatives through a function, options, beliefs and current intentions of the agent and from these variations determines a set of options, which are equivalent to the desires or preferences (Wooldridge 2002).

4 Results and discussions

4.1 Spatial design of the ecological remediation

As mentioned in the section of methods used for spatial analysis, the QGIS tool was employed for the delimitation the area of interest (figure 11), using a vector layer in the form of a polygon, to then generate a grid from the previously created layer. An area of 50x50 m² was established for each grid, thus obtaining a total number of 2619 grids with a total area of 654.75 hectares (figure 11, the sum of the yellow and light blue grids). It is worth mentioning that these grids became known as "parcels". This area of interest contains our study area (Fig. 2), where an identification of the habitats bordering (outside) this area was carried out.

Then, four habitats were identified for our study interest, which were categorized into areas with no vegetation at all, called habitat type 1, forests as habitat type 2, pastures as habitat type 3 and areas with sparsely vegetation as habitat type 4.

The areas identified for each of these habitats outside the study area were as follows: the presence of pastures is equivalent to 567 plots, which translates into 141.75 hectares (figure 13, orange plots); forests have 1478 plots, equivalent to 369.5 hectares (figure 13, green plots); areas with little vegetation were not considered when identifying and classifying the habitats; and finally, the

areas with no vegetation at all are equivalent to the tailing pond (figure 13, blue plots), which represents 574 plots, corresponding to 143.5 hectares.

Figure 13 Identification and classification of the 4 habitat types in the S0 (initial scenario).

Once the categorization and identification of the habitats was done, 10 possible planting scenarios were projected in the study area, from the percentage point of view of each of four habitats. Each scenario was represented separately as a new vector layer in the form of a polygon with its

Table 5 Percentages of habitat types 2, 3 and 4 established for the design and projection of the 10 different scenarios in the study area.

Scenario	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)
S1	10%	10%	80%
S2	20%	20%	60%
S3	30%	30%	40%
S4	40%	40%	20%
S5	50%	50%	0%
S6	10%	30%	60%
S7	30%	10%	60%
S8	20%	60%	20%
S9	80%	20%	0%
S10	100%	0%	0%

Table 6 Number of plots of habitat types 2, 3 and 4 established for the design and projection of the 10 different scenarios in the study area.

Scenario	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)
S1	57	57	459
S2	115	115	344
S3	172	172	230
S4	230	230	115
S5	287	287	0
S6	57	172	344
S7	172	57	344
S8	115	344	115
S9	459	115	0
S10	574	0	0

For the structuring of these percentages presented in the table 5 for each of these scenarios, a systematic incipient level was used, where a progressive growth of the percentages of each type of habitat was applied, in order to obtain different values, proportions and approach for the 10 scenarios. For the transfer of information from percentages of habitats planted to the number of plots to be planted, the conversion of this data was carried out, obtaining the results shown in the table 6. Subsequently, these scenarios will be tested and evaluated from the point of view of presence and absence of the respective species.

Figure 14 Scenario 1.

Figure 15 Scenario 2.

Figure 16 Scenario 3.

Figure 17 Scenario 4.

Figure 18 Scenario 5.

Figure 19 Scenario 6.

Figure 20 Scenario 7.

Figure 21 Scenario 8.

Figure 22 Scenario 9.

Figure 23 Scenario 10.

4.2 Connectivity between habitats

The planting design of the habitats in the study zone was focused on the two types of connectivity. The first type of connectivity, called spatial, is mainly related to the direct contact of the surfaces of the same habitat. Due to the proximity of the surfaces, spatial dispersal activities or, in other words, the home range of each species are mainly developed. The habitat preferences of the species *Carabus violaceus* and *Apodemus sylvaticus* and their respective surfaces, relate with this type of connectivity as follows. Where the pastures already existing in the area of interest (outside the tailing pond) with respect to the pastures planted in the study area. The same methodology was performed for the forest type habitat. The second type of connectivity is the functional type, which has attracting attributes for the respective species, from the point of view of spatial-temporal scales, with respect to the periods of reproduction or hibernation. In the same way this type of connectivity influences the percentage of hunting or finding food by predators. This type of connectivity was evaluated in the following way, where habitats outside the tailing dam, such as pastures, see planted habitats, in this case forests, as a "gateway". And the same was done for the forest-type habitats outside the study zone with respect to the planted pastures in the tailing pond.

From the strategic point of view of the project, this practice is observed as a secondary strategy of reconstruction, where through the habilitation of these contact surfaces, a tropho-dynamic model, and the development of ecosystemic relationships can be obtained, or due to the need of the species and their periodic seasonal behavior, it can be observed as a refuge.

To demonstrate the feasibility of the contact of the surfaces of these habitats with each other, a graphic model was designed and elaborated (figure 24), in which the different scenarios created in the study area were included as input data, to then give way to the selection of an attribute, which is translated to select a type of habitat, in this case of the interior of the study area in relation to the habitat that is outside the study area but within the area of interest. When both attributes (habitats) related to each other are spatially selected, we make a new selection but in this case of location type, where we only take into consideration the habitats that touch each other in an exterior-interior way, thus giving a percentage of success to the individuals that move to the planted plots.

Figure 24 graphic model (made in QGIS) that relates the connection of the habitats outside the study area and those that were artificially planted in it.

As a result of the relationships established between the habitats found outside the study area with those found inside (planted), in addition to the use of the graphic model (figure 24), the following results were obtained. With respect to the direct spatial connectivity in relation to the 10 scenarios, tables 7 and 8 were obtained, which are complemented with their respective graphs, 1 and 2. And, the functional connectivity is demonstrated by tables 9 and 10, and graphs 3 and 4.

In relation to the results obtained with respect to the spatial connectivity, a correlation from the statistical point of view is evident. Theoretically speaking, it is estimated that a greater number of planted plots is equivalent to a greater spatial connectivity. In our case, graph 1 (pasture-pasture relationship) shows a tendency of growth of the pastures type habitat in scenario 1 (S1) to scenario 5 (S5), where extreme scenarios (S6, S7, S8, S9 and S10) fluctuate greatly, where as the percentage of pastures decreases, the percentage of forest plots increases, thus generating a barrier effect for the connectivity that is to be generated.

Also, it is assumed that as the percentage of pastures habitats decreases, their connectivity capacity also decreases. It is worth mentioning that the positioning of the plots plays a key role in the representation of this type of connectivity. As can be seen in scenario number 7 (S7) of table 7, it presents the highest number of direct connectivity with respect to the outside of the study area, but also presents the lowest percentage of planted pastures in the study area.

This type of spatial connectivity is directly related to the quality of mobility and dispersal of species. In relation to our study material, it is related to the species *Carabus violaceus*, where its

relationship with pastures habitats is that of primary producer and first order consumer. The qualitative evaluation of this home range performed by individuals belonging to the species *Carabus violaceus* is based on the displacement from an old pastures habitat to a new planted pastures, where this active or passive displacement will be analyzed and represented by the potential use of these new planted habitats.

Table 7 PASTURES – INTERIOR / PASTURES – EXTERIOR

Scenario	PASTURES - INTERIOR	PASTURES - EXTERIOR
S1	10%	26
S2	20%	27
S3	30%	29
S4	40%	30
S5	50%	25
S6	30%	27
S7	10%	33
S8	60%	29
S9	20%	31
S10	0%	0

Graphic 1 HAB 1 (INTERIOR) - TYPE 3 – PASTURE / HAB 2 (EXTERIOR) - TYPE 3 - PASTURE

Similarly, Table 8 and Graphic 2 show a direct spatial connectivity, where the correlation of this type of forest-forest habitat with respect to its spatial positioning, in comparison with the pasture-pasture relationship, these results show a different behavior.

In this case, it can be evidenced with respect to graphic number 2, a correlation and growth trend in the first 5 scenarios and the last two, where this type of habitat (forest type) is "independent" with respect to pastures (which also represent a much smaller amount outside the study area compared to forest type habitats), This "independence" is based on the data provided in table 8, where in graph 2 a decreasing situation can also be seen in scenarios 6, 7 and 8, due to the percentages of habitats planted inside the study area.

With respect to both results in relation to direct spatial connectivity, a higher spatial percentage of remediated forest-forest type habitats can be seen in contrast to pastures-pastures type habitats. In the case of forest-forest type habitats, they present a gateway for the recolonization of the study area by the species *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Table 8 FOREST – INTERIOR / FOREST - EXTERIOR

Scenario	FOREST - INTERIOR	FOREST - EXTERIOR
S1	10%	138
S2	20%	181
S3	30%	178
S4	40%	176
S5	50%	186
S6	10%	160
S7	30%	160
S8	20%	178
S9	80%	145
S10	100%	187

Graphic 2 HAB 1 (INTERIOR) - TYPE 2 - FOREST / HAB 2 (EXTERIOR) - TYPE 2 - FOREST

In contrast to the cases carried out in relation to direct spatial connectivity, studies were also carried out in relation to the second type of connectivity, which is called functional. In this way, two comparative relationships were developed in terms of the presence outside the study area and planting of the respective habitats.

The first results with respect to this type of functional connectivity were based on the relationship between the planted pastures inside the study area and the plots of the bordering habitats belonging to the forest habitat type (table 9). In which, the growth of the interfaces between the existing forest surfaces and the planted pastures observed in graph number 3, in scenarios S4, S5 and S8, favor the preyed and predator type analysis, besides being considered as a control mechanism, since a relationship of first order consumer with a second order consumer is carried out.

In our case study *Apodemus sylvaticus*, being a species that has a preference for forest-type habitats, besides belonging to a trophodynamic module, requires and possesses the need for dispersal with the objective, for example, of hunting for food.

Due to the above, it was generated the relationship of the bordering habitats of forest type in relation to the planted habitats of pasture type, which generate the opportunities of the individuals of *Apodemus sylvaticus* the transfer of matter or biomass, which is not carried out in the same population, so the mobilization of this species is relevant.

Table 9 PASTURES – INTERIOR / FOREST – EXTERIOR

Scenario	PASTURES - INTERIOR	FOREST - EXTERIOR
S1	10%	111
S2	20%	93
S3	30%	132
S4	40%	76
S5	50%	84
S6	30%	142
S7	10%	81
S8	60%	131
S9	20%	108
S10	0%	0

Graphic 3 HAB 1 (INTERIOR) - TYPE 3 - PASTURES / HAB 2 (EXTERIOR) - TYPE 2 - FOREST

Similarly, the type of functional connectivity was evaluated with another example, considering the habitats planted in the interior of the study area, which were of the forest type, and the habitats bordering it, which were of the pastures type, which are represented in Table 10 and Graph 4.

In graph 4 it can be observed that in scenarios S4, S7 and S9, interfaces or intersections are generated between the two habitats that are related, where they are predicted as zones of greater success with respect to the individuals of *Carabus violaceus* that can move to the reconstructed habitats. In the case of *Carabus violaceus* individuals, their movement to the remediated habitats may be due to the search for food, shelter or even for hibernation periods, which are less active.

The variations observed in graph 4 with respect to the presence of pastures, shows an emphasis on the most populated areas outside the study area, and this can also be seen by the orange plots (which refer to pastures habitats) in figure 13.

Table 10 FOREST – INTERIOR / PASTURES - EXTERIOR

Scenario	FOREST - INTERIOR	PASTURES - EXTERIOR
S1	10%	5
S2	20%	12
S3	30%	13
S4	40%	11
S5	50%	22
S6	10%	15
S7	30%	5
S8	20%	13
S9	80%	12
S10	100%	33

Graphic 4 HAB 1 (INTERIOR) - TYPE 2 - FOREST / HAB 2 (EXTERIOR) - TYPE 3 – PASTURES

4.3 Use of remediated habitats

For the estimation of habitat use by *Apodemus sylvaticus* and *Carabus violaceus* species, a graphical modeling in QGIS represented by figure ... was performed. The first type of data is represented by the 10 scenarios carried out exclusively in the study area and the second set of input data is represented by the number of intersections (called waypoints) of the respective species with the habitats corresponding to each one, in terms of direct spatial connectivity.

Then a count was made of these waypoints per individual of each species with respect to their preferred habitat. In our case study, the species *Apodemus sylvaticus* was related to the use of planted forest habitat in the study area and *Carabus violaceus* to the habitat type of planted pastures. The total number of intersections by species was then finalized with a new vector layer in the form of a polygon for each scenario in part.

Figure 25 graphical model to represent the number of intersections by study species in relation to their preferred habitat planted in the study area.

4.3.1 *Carabus violaceus*

To obtain the dataset with respect to the number of intersections of *Carabus violaceus*, a spatial modeling was performed with the Repast Symphony tool (figure 26) with the use of 23 individuals in the area of interest, the area of interest was used as a base to observe how the individuals of this species will move with respect to the remediated habitats in the study area. Each individual presents a non-linear independence of dispersion, as can be observed in Figure ... each individual is represented by a yellow dot and its intersection with the habitats in the area of interest are represented by the white to deep pink colored squares or plots. The variation of the colors depends on the number of intersections that are made with the habitats present, where as the number of intersections or the use of habitats is greater, the color becomes more intense. ´

Figure 26 spatial dispersal model of the species *Carabus violaceus* in the area of interest.

The data obtained in the Repast Symphony tool were exported to the QGIS tool (figure 27) to identify which types of planted habitats present in the study area were intercepted by these 23 individuals of *Carabus violaceus* and with what frequency.

Figure 27 waypoints belonging to the species *Carabus violaceus* in the area of interest.

After the dataset was exported to the QGIS tool, these data were evaluated in each of the 10 scenarios projected in the study area, thus obtaining how often *Carabus violaceus* intercepts with the plots of each of the planted habitats.

Specific values were obtained for each of these habitats and a total of these, characterized by the frequency of use. it is important to mention that these data are represented by the tables 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20.

Table 11 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S1 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	36	36	333	405
1	4	2	15	21
2	2	4	5	11
3			7	7
4		3	11	14
5	2	1	10	13
6	1	2	4	7
7			7	7
8	3	1	2	6
9			2	2
10	2	2	3	7
11	1		3	4
12	2	1	6	9
13			4	4
14			6	6
15			3	3
16	1	1	3	5
17	1	2	2	5
18			3	3
19			6	6
20			3	3
21			2	2
22			2	2
23			2	2
26	1	1	3	5
27			2	2
29			1	1
30			1	1
32			2	2
33	1			1
34			1	1
35			1	1
36			1	1
38			1	1
39			1	1
41			1	1
46		1	1	2
Total	57	57	460	574

Table 12 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S2 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	72	80	253	405
1	7	4	10	21
2	2	3	6	11
3	1	2	4	7
4	3	4	7	14
5	3	4	6	13
6	4	2	1	7
7		4	3	7
8	3	1	2	6
9		1	1	2
10	2	1	4	7
11	1	1	2	4
12	4	1	4	9
13	1		3	4
14		1	5	6
15	1		2	3
16	1	1	3	5
17	2		3	5
18	1		2	3
19		1	5	6
20		1	2	3
21	1		1	2
22	1		1	2
23			2	2
26	2	1	2	5
27			2	2
29			1	1
30			1	1
32			2	2
33			1	1
34		1		1
35			1	1
36		1		1
38			1	1
39	1			1
41	1			1
46	1		1	2
Total	115	115	344	574

Table 13 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S3 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	111	121	173	405
1	9	6	6	21
2	4	4	3	11
3	3	3	1	7
4	3	3	8	14
5	4	1	8	13
6	4	3		7
7	1		6	7
8	3	3		6
9	1		1	2
10	3	1	3	7
11	2	1	1	4
12	2	4	3	9
13	2	1	1	4
14	1	5		6
15		3		3
16	1	3	1	5
17	3	2		5
18	2		1	3
19	2		4	6
20	1	1	1	3
21			2	2
22		1	1	2
23	1		1	2
26	3	2		5
27		2		2
29			1	1
30			1	1
32		1	1	2
33	1			1
34			1	1
35	1			1
36			1	1
38		1		1
39	1			1
41	1			1
46	2			2
Total	172	172	230	574

Table 14 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S4 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	148	165	92	405
1	11	8	2	21
2	6	4	1	11
3	3	4		7
4	7	7		14
5	4	7	2	13
6	6	1		7
7	4	2	1	7
8	4	2		6
9		1	1	2
10	2	3	2	7
11	1	2	1	4
12	4	4	1	9
13	1	3		4
14	4	2		6
15	1	1	1	3
16	4		1	5
17	4		1	5
18		1	2	3
19	1	4	1	6
20	1	1	1	3
21	1	1		2
22	1	1		2
23		1	1	2
26	3	1	1	5
27	2			2
29			1	1
30			1	1
32		1	1	2
33		1		1
34	1			1
35	1			1
36	1			1
38		1		1
39	1			1
41	1			1
46	1	1		2
Total	229	230	115	574

Table 15 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S5 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots		
	Habitats		
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Total
0	199	206	405
1	12	9	21
2	2	9	11
3	1	6	7
4	7	7	14
5	9	4	13
6	5	2	7
7	4	3	7
8	6		6
9	1	1	2
10	3	4	7
11	3	1	4
12	5	4	9
13	3	1	4
14	2	4	6
15	2	1	3
16	2	3	5
17	3	2	5
18		3	3
19	3	3	6
20	2	1	3
21		2	2
22	1	1	2
23	2		2
26	2	3	5
27	1	1	2
29	1		1
30		1	1
32	1	1	2
33		1	1
34		1	1
35		1	1
36		1	1
38	1		1
39	1		1
41	1		1
46	2		2
Total	287	287	574

Table 16 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S6 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	36	116	253	405
1	3	11	7	21
2		7	4	11
3	2	2	3	7
4		6	8	14
5	2	2	9	13
6		4	3	7
7		1	6	7
8	2	3	1	6
9		1	1	2
10	3		4	7
11		2	2	4
12	3	3	3	9
13	1		3	4
14		1	5	6
15		1	2	3
16	1	2	2	5
17	1	2	2	5
18		2	1	3
19			6	6
20			3	3
21		1	1	2
22			2	2
23			2	2
26	1	2	2	5
27			2	2
29			1	1
30			1	1
32	1		1	2
33			1	1
34			1	1
35			1	1
36		1		1
38		1		1
39			1	1
41		1		1
46	1		1	2
Total	57	172	345	574

Table 17 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S7 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	118	33	254	405
1	7	3	11	21
2	3	3	5	11
3	3	1	3	7
4	5	1	8	14
5	1	2	10	13
6	3	1	3	7
7	1	1	5	7
8	3	1	2	6
9			2	2
10		4	3	7
11	1	1	2	4
12	5	1	3	9
13		1	3	4
14	2	1	3	6
15	1		2	3
16	2	1	2	5
17	3		2	5
18	1		2	3
19	2		4	6
20	2		1	3
21			2	2
22			2	2
23	1		1	2
26	3	1	1	5
27			2	2
29			1	1
30			1	1
32		1	1	2
33	1			1
34			1	1
35			1	1
36	1			1
38			1	1
39	1			1
41			1	1
46	2			2
Total	172	57	345	574

Table 18 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S8 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pastures (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	76	246	83	405
1	3	13	5	21
2	3	5	3	11
3	2	5		7
4		10	4	14
5	5	4	4	13
6	2	4	1	7
7		5	2	7
8	3	3		6
9		2		2
10	2	5		7
11	3	1		4
12	3	4	2	9
13	1	2	1	4
14	1	5		6
15	1	2		3
16	1	3	1	5
17	3	1	1	5
18		3		3
19	1	3	2	6
20	1	2		3
21		2		2
22		1	1	2
23		2		2
26	2	3		5
27		2		2
29		1		1
30		1		1
32	1		1	2
33		1		1
34			1	1
35			1	1
36		1		1
38			1	1
39			1	1
41		1		1
46	1	1		2
Total	115	344	115	574

Table 19 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S9 by *Carabus violaceus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots		
	Habitats		
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Total
0	334	71	405
1	17	4	21
2	9	2	11
3	4	3	7
4	10	4	14
5	7	6	13
6	5	2	7
7	5	2	7
8	5	1	6
9	2		2
10	3	4	7
11	2	2	4
12	6	3	9
13	2	2	4
14	6		6
15	3		3
16	3	2	5
17	4	1	5
18	3		3
19	5	1	6
20	3		3
21	2		2
22	2		2
23	2		2
26	3	2	5
27	1	1	2
29	1		1
30	1		1
32	1	1	2
33	1		1
34	1		1
35	1		1
36	1		1
38	1		1
39	1		1
41	1		1
46	1	1	2
Total	459	115	574

Table 20 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S10 by *Carabus violaceus*.

	Number of plots	
Count NUMPOINTS	Habitats	
Frequency	Forest (2)	Total
0	405	405
1	21	21
2	11	11
3	7	7
4	14	14
5	13	13
6	7	7
7	7	7
8	6	6
9	2	2
10	7	7
11	4	4
12	9	9
13	4	4
14	6	6
15	3	3
16	5	5
17	5	5
18	3	3
19	6	6
20	3	3
21	2	2
22	2	2
23	2	2
26	5	5
27	2	2
29	1	1
30	1	1
32	2	2
33	1	1
34	1	1
35	1	1
36	1	1
38	1	1
39	1	1
41	1	1
46	2	2
Total	574	574

4.3.2 *Apodemus sylvaticus*

The direct spatial connectivity was evaluated for the habitats preferred by the species *Apodemus sylvaticus*, where with the use of the Respast Symphony tool (figure 28) it was possible to obtain waypoint data, represented in the figure, with reference to the dispersion of this species and its intersection with the habitats present in the study area. Similarly, 23 individuals of the species *Apodemus sylvaticus* were used for this modeling, introducing the respective data on spatial dispersion.

Figure 28 spatial dispersal model of the species *Apodemus sylvaticus* in the area of interest.

After obtaining the dataset regarding the use of the habitats belonging to the area of interest, these were exported and displayed in the QGIS tool represented by the figure 29, where the results can be evaluated more precisely in terms of the number of interactions and intersections with the planted habitats belonging to the study area and the respective species.

Figure 29 waypoints belonging to the species *Apodemus sylvaticus* in the area of interest.

For the representation of the results of each of these 10 scenarios with respect to the dispersion (waypoints) of the species *Apodemus sylvaticus*, tables 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29 and 30 were generated, which have the frequency or number of intersections made by this species in the different habitats planted in the study area, and also provides information on how many of these plots of each habitat were used in each scenario.

Table 21 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S1 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	32	27	307	366
1	2	1	20	23
2	2	1	12	15
3	3	3	14	20
4		2	7	9
5		2	10	12
6	1	3	10	14
7	4	2	10	16
8		4	11	15
9	1	1	11	13
10	3	1	6	10
11	1	1	8	10
12	1	2	4	7
13			3	3
14	1	1	2	4
15			3	3
16	1	3	1	5
17		1		1
18			6	6
19	1		3	4
20			1	1
21	1			1
22			1	1
23		1		1
24	1			1
25	1			1
26			1	1
27	1		2	3
31		1	2	3
32			2	2
44			1	1
46			1	1
47			1	1
Total	57	57	460	574

Table 22 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S2 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pastures (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	70	66	230	366
1	2	4	17	23
2	3	2	10	15
3	6	4	10	20
4	2	4	3	9
5	1	2	9	12
6	3	5	6	14
7	9	2	5	16
8	5	3	7	15
9		4	9	13
10	2	2	6	10
11	2		8	10
12		3	4	7
13		1	2	3
14		4		4
15	1	1	1	3
16	2	1	2	5
17			1	1
18	2	2	2	6
19	1		3	4
20		1		1
21			1	1
22			1	1
23	1			1
24	1			1
25	1			1
26		1		1
27			3	3
31		1	2	3
32		2		2
44			1	1
46	1			1
47			1	1
Total	115	115	344	574

Table 23 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S3 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	104	102	160	366
1	6	11	6	23
2	3	4	8	15
3	5	5	10	20
4	5	1	3	9
5	2	4	6	12
6	6	4	4	14
7	7	5	4	16
8	5	4	6	15
9	4	6	3	13
10	3	4	3	10
11	3	1	6	10
12	3	1	3	7
13		3		3
14	2	1	1	4
15		2	1	3
16	2	2	1	5
17		1		1
18	3	2	1	6
19	2	1	1	4
20			1	1
21	1			1
22		1		1
23		1		1
24	1			1
25	1			1
26	1			1
27	1	2		3
31		2	1	3
32	1	1		2
44	1			1
46		1		1
47			1	1
Total	172	172	230	574

Table 24 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S4 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	145	144	77	366
1	7	11	5	23
2	2	6	7	15
3	9	8	3	20
4	5	3	1	9
5	6	1	5	12
6	5	7	2	14
7	7	7	2	16
8	6	4	5	15
9	5	5	3	13
10	3	7		10
11	4	3	3	10
12	4	3		7
13	1	2		3
14	2	2		4
15	1	2		3
16	3	2		5
17		1		1
18	6			6
19	1	2	1	4
20		1		1
21		1		1
22		1		1
23	1			1
24	1			1
25	1			1
26		1		1
27	1	2		3
31		2	1	3
32	2			2
44		1		1
46	1			1
47		1		1
Total	229	230	115	574

Table 25 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S5 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots		
	Habitats		
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Total
0	184	182	366
1	8	15	23
2	10	5	15
3	10	10	20
4	5	4	9
5	7	5	12
6	7	7	14
7	8	8	16
8	9	6	15
9	6	7	13
10	6	4	10
11	4	6	10
12	1	6	7
13		3	3
14	1	3	4
15	2	1	3
16	4	1	5
17	1		1
18	3	3	6
19	1	3	4
20		1	1
21		1	1
22		1	1
23	1		1
24	1		1
25	1		1
26	1		1
27	2	1	3
31	2	1	3
32		2	2
44	1		1
46	1		1
47		1	1
Total	287	287	574

Table 26 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S6 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	34	109	223	366
1		12	11	23
2	1	1	13	15
3	2	5	13	20
4	1	2	6	9
5	1	3	8	12
6	1	8	5	14
7	4	4	8	16
8	2	3	10	15
9	1	3	9	13
10	1	3	6	10
11	2	2	6	10
12		3	4	7
13			3	3
14		3	1	4
15		2	1	3
16	2	2	1	5
17		1		1
18	1		5	6
19	1	1	2	4
20			1	1
21			1	1
22		1		1
23		1		1
24	1			1
25	1			1
26		1		1
27	1	1	1	3
31			3	3
32		1	1	2
44			1	1
46			1	1
47			1	1
Total	57	172	345	574

Table 27 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S7 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots			
	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	103	27	236	366
1	8	1	14	23
2	5	1	9	15
3	6	6	8	20
4	3		6	9
5	6	1	5	12
6	4	2	8	14
7	6	3	7	16
8	6	1	8	15
9	5	1	7	13
10	2		8	10
11	3	1	6	10
12	2	2	3	7
13	2		1	3
14		3	1	4
15	1	1	1	3
16	1	3	1	5
17	1			1
18	2	2	2	6
19	1		3	4
20			1	1
21	1			1
22	1			1
23		1		1
24	1			1
25	1			1
26			1	1
27		1	2	3
31			3	3
32	1		1	2
44			1	1
46			1	1
47			1	1
Total	172	57	345	574

Table 28 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S8 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

	Number of plots			
Count NUMPOINTS	Habitats			
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Sparsely vegetated (4)	Total
0	66	213	87	366
1	3	18	2	23
2	4	11		15
3	4	14	2	20
4	2	7		9
5		9	3	12
6	2	9	3	14
7	8	6	2	16
8	3	8	4	15
9	4	7	2	13
10	3	6	1	10
11	2	5	3	10
12	1	5	1	7
13		3		3
14		4		4
15		1	2	3
16	3	2		5
17		1		1
18	2	3	1	6
19	1	3		4
20		1		1
21		1		1
22		1		1
23	1			1
24	1			1
25	1			1
26		1		1
27	2	1		3
31		2	1	3
32	1	1		2
44	1			1
46		1		1
47			1	1
Total	115	344	115	574

Table 29 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S9 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots		
	Habitats		
Frequency	Forest (2)	Pasture (3)	Total
0	312	54	366
1	18	5	23
2	13	2	15
3	14	6	20
4	7	2	9
5	10	2	12
6	9	5	14
7	11	5	16
8	12	3	15
9	9	4	13
10	6	4	10
11	8	2	10
12	4	3	7
13	3		3
14	1	3	4
15	2	1	3
16	2	3	5
17	1		1
18	5	1	6
19	2	2	4
20		1	1
21	1		1
22	1		1
23		1	1
24		1	1
25		1	1
26		1	1
27	1	2	3
31	2	1	3
32	2		2
44	1		1
46	1		1
47	1		1
Total	459	115	574

Table 30 Frequency of use of planted habitats in S10 by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Count NUMPOINTS	Number of plots	
	Habitats	
Frequency	Forest (2)	Total
0	366	366
1	23	23
2	15	15
3	20	20
4	9	9
5	12	12
6	14	14
7	16	16
8	15	15
9	13	13
10	10	10
11	10	10
12	7	7
13	3	3
14	4	4
15	3	3
16	5	5
17	1	1
18	6	6
19	4	4
20	1	1
21	1	1
22	1	1
23	1	1
24	1	1
25	1	1
26	1	1
27	3	3
31	3	3
32	2	2
44	1	1
46	1	1
47	1	1
Total	574	574

4.4 Connectivity between habitats vs use of remediated habitats

In this last subchapter we will compare the results obtained from the connection of the planted habitats in the study area and those bordering them on the outside, with the use of the remediated habitats by the species *Apodemus sylvaticus* and *Carabus violaceus*, separately. It is worth mentioning that only the direct spatial connectivity of the species with respect to their habitat preference will be evaluated.

One of our hypotheses at the beginning of this project was the following: where there is the greatest number of connectivity between the plots of the new habitats planted in the study area and the old habitats, there will be a greater potential for utilization of the new planted space by individual species.

For the validation of this hypothesis, tables number 31 and 32 were generated, which will be compared with tables number 7 and 8, and graphs 1 and 2, present in subchapter 3.2 "Connectivity between habitats".

The Table 31 presents the frequency intervals obtained from the planted pastures habitats in the 10 projected scenarios, which will be compared with Table 7 and Graph 1, where these intervals were classified in the table number 31 by low frequency intervals, represented by the color yellow, medium frequency intervals, represented by the color blue and, finally, high frequency intervals represented by the color green.

These tables and graphs represent the direct spatial connectivity with respect to the habitats and how these can be used by the species *Carabus violaceus*, where it was obtained with respect to the table 31 a top 3 of habitats, where the following criterion was used, where the scenarios that present a greater number of medium intervals compared to high intervals will have a higher value and consideration.

This top 3 of scenarios is composed of the scenarios, S8 with 30 plots belonging to the medium interval and 11 plots belonging to the high interval, S5 with 25 plots belonging to the medium interval and 10 plots belonging to the high interval, and S3 with 20 plots belonging to the medium interval and 6 plots belonging to the high interval. From the point of view of the results represented in Table 4, S8 presented 60% of planted habitats with a result of 29 contact zones, S5 presented 50% of planted habitats with a result of 25 contact zones and S3 presented 30% of planted habitats with a result of 29 contact zones.

But it is worth mentioning that it is also shown in the Table 4 that in S7 there were 10% of planted habitats with a result of 33 contact zones, which has the largest number of contact zones. Due to

the above mentioned, it can be concluded that in the case of the pastures-pastures relationship and the utilization of the new planted habitats, it does not have a direct relationship with the contact zones, but presents a relationship with the amount and percentage of planted plots in the study area in relation to the percentage of utilization by the species *Carabus violaceus*, thus obtaining S8 as the optimal scenario for the utilization of the remediated space with respect to the species *Carabus violaceus*.

Table 31 frequency intervals of the resulting intersection frequencies for planted pastures habitats with the species *Carabus violaceus* for each of the 10 projected scenarios.

	Number of plots									
Frequency	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
0-11	51	107	146	206	252	155	51	303	101	0
12-23	4	5	20	19	25	12	4	30	9	0
26-46	2	3	6	5	10	5	2	11	5	0
TOTAL PLOTS	57	115	172	230	287	172	57	344	115	0

In relation to the second set of results regarding direct spatial connectivity, Table 8 and Graph 2 relate forest-forest habitats. These results will be contrasted with the results represented in table 32.

The Table 32 presents the frequency intervals obtained from the planted forests habitats in the 10 projected scenarios, which will be compared with Table 8 and Graph 2, where these intervals were classified in the table 32 by low frequency intervals, represented by the color yellow, medium frequency intervals, represented by the color blue and, finally, high frequency intervals represented by the color orange.

The top 3 scenarios that were most used by the *Apodemus sylvaticus* species, S10 with 45 plots belonging to the medium interval and 16 plots belonging to the high interval, S9 with 29 plots belonging to the medium interval and 9 plots belonging to the high interval and S4 with 22 plots belonging to the medium interval and 7 plots belonging to the high interval.

Contrasting these results with those shown in Table 8, S10 has 100% of habitats planted with a result of 187 contact zones, S9 has 80% of habitats planted with a result of 145 contact zones and S4 has 40% of habitats planted with a result of 176 contact zones. In both cases of the results presented in tables 8 and 32, it can be seen that scenario 10 represents the optimal case for use by *Apodemus sylvaticus*.

Table 32 frequency intervals of the resulting intersection frequencies for planted pastures habitats with the species *Apodemus sylvaticus* for each of the 10 projected scenarios.

Frequency	Number of plots									
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
0-10	48	103	150	200	260	48	154	99	421	513
11-21	6	8	16	22	17	6	14	9	29	45
22-47	3	4	6	7	10	3	4	7	9	16
TOTAL PLOTS	57	115	172	229	287	57	172	115	459	574

Since tables 31 and 32 present the individual results for each species and its preferred habitat, table number 33 was generated, which presents 3 types of intervals with respect to the frequency of interceptions by *Apodemus sylvaticus* and *Carabus violaceus* species, where the low interval is represented by the yellow color, the medium interval by the orange color and the high interval by the green color.

Table number 33 was used to integrate the results of both species with the totality of the habitats planted in the study area. Scenario S5 was identified as the optimal scenario for the use of both species in the study area with the remediated habitats, which presented 42 plots belonging to the medium interval and 21 plots belonging to the high interval.

Table 33 frequency intervals of the resulting intersection frequencies for planted habitats with the species *Apodemus sylvaticus* and *Carabus violaceus* for each of the 10 projected scenarios.

Frequency	Number of plots									
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
0-10	99	209	295	404	511	201	204	401	520	513
11-21	10	14	36	41	42	20	19	37	40	45
22-47	5	7	13	14	21	8	6	21	14	16
TOTAL PLOTS	114	230	344	459	574	229	229	459	574	574

5 Conclusion

For objective 1, to screen the literature relevant to the dispersal of mobile organisms on remediated tailing dams:

- The most common approaches to modeling dispersal in landscape ecology are the least-cost models and individual-based dispersal models.
- Space use theories tend to be developed specifically for various groups of organisms. Regarding calibrating and validating the models, besides scenario development, one would need tight cooperation between landscape ecologists/theoretical biologists and the experts in the groups of organisms.
- The relationship between ecological connectivity and the production of ecosystem services is well-established in the scientific literature. In areas with the mining and processing industry in their structure, the research is mediated by methodological approaches (e.g., critical metal concentration, bioconcentration factor, lead isotopes, tree ring records), by case studies, usually ecological systems with large mining disasters. There is a new research direction dealing with the spatial variation problem, including the landscape connectivity effects. There is also an increasing presence of explicit approaches to ecosystem services in such areas, from local to river basin scale.
- Mapping with Citespace the literature about modeling the dispersal of beetles, frogs/amphibians, rodents/small mammals, and snakes/reptiles has shown that:
 - For beetles there are three clusters including the keyword ecosystem service.
 - For amphibians there is a single cluster including the keyword ecosystem service.
 - For the other groups of organisms, modeling the dispersal was not yet intensively related to the problem of ecosystem service to generate clusters of literature.
 - For amphibians there is a cluster including the keyword surface mine, dealing with the toxicity of ponds formed in closed surface mines on amphibians dispersed in such habitats.
 - For the other groups of organisms, there are no clusters with the keywords mining, surface mine, smelter, tailing, dump, or industry.
- The problem of dispersal of organisms to remediated tailing dams in relation to the production of ecosystem service of the integrating landscape has not been approached by many scientists in the past, underlining the novelty of the second objective of this thesis.

For objective 2, to simulate the dispersal of two selected species in different scenarios of spatial design of the vegetation microhabitats on the tailing dam:

- Habitat remediation was performed using combined solutions, whereby habitat distributions are tested to favor direct spatial connectivity and functional connectivity. The proposed method of analysis to favor connectivity of both types shows positive results.
- With respect to the working hypothesis whether the remediated pastures type habitats have the capacity to benefit the species *Carabus violaceus*, the scenario that is considered the most optimal for this species is scenario number 8. Similarly, the installation of forest-type habitats in the study area with respect to the projected scenarios, scenario S10 favors the spatial dispersion of the species *Apodemus sylvaticus*. This type of factor with respect to the spatial dispersion of the species is dependent on the direct spatial connectivity (direct contact between habitats) of the respective habitats and their percentage present. **For the integration of both species in the study area, the S5 scenario was considered the most likely scenario for the successful integration of these species and the remediated habitats.**
- In contrast, the functional connectivity depends on the distribution of the mosaics of the respective plots in the study area. Functional connectivity was not fully tested and developed as a method of analysis in this project, whereby considering the percentages or numbers of plots of habitat types that favor both species are the most relevant for functional connectivity, thus leaving the topic open for future research and data analysis.
- The testing of the maximum entropy calculation method with the Maxent instrument was proposed, but due to the lack of data sets for the characterization of the habitat status parameters of the area (ecosystem status parameters), because our spatial scale is considered very small, the data obtained were considered not very influential and not relevant for this category of studies.
- In addition, the solution of using total entropy is not the best solution for our aim, because this instrument performs the selection between habitats with a degree of similarity. Considering that the remediated habitats are planted in an area where there is no previous presence of habitats that can be compared with these new habitats. It is also worth mentioning that the ecological remediation activity does not represent a reinstallation of existing or pre-existing habitats, but rather new habitats are used to carry out this activity.

The results of the first objective can be further developed in a review article and those of the second objective in a primary research article.

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Appendix 1 Procedure for Citespace basic use.

First step:

Elimination of duplicates

Before the elimination of the duplicate data, subfolders of the data to be filtered must be created, where the base/initial/gross data must be added in the "BRUT/INITIAL DATA" folder and the data already filtered by citespace need a folder called "FILTERED DATA" where the data without duplicates will be stored.

In citespace it is done in the following way:

- Click on DATA in the menu
- Click on IMPORT/EXPORT

For the criteria selection, it MUST be in the mode "TOP N"

- INPUT: the data from the "BRUT/INITIAL DATA" folder is added.
- OUTPUT: the "FILTERED DATA" folder is added.
- SAVE

Stage 2, cluster generation:

- NEW PROJECT (title: use the same name of the folder in the project)
 - o PROJECT HOME: large folder, e.g. "Ant_AND_dispersal_AND_modelling"
 - o DATA DIRECTORY: select the folder with the "FILTERED DATA"
 - o SAVE

- Define the "TIME SLICING" time period in which the documents will be taken into account.
- GO

- VIZUALIZE (wait until the figure shows little or no movement)
- STOP

- Then the image will change and should look like the following image:

Then click on:

- ALL IN ONE

- TITLU (T) -> OK

- After pressing OK, the image should change to something shown in the following image.

Then click on:

- TIMELINE VIEW

- After clicking "TIMELINE VIEW", the image should change to something shown in the following image.

- CLUSTERS (menu) -> SAVE CLUSTER INFORMATION

- CLUSTERS (menu) -> SUMMARY TABLE | WHITELISTS

- Then a demo page should open as in the following image:

- After that, click on “SAVE/SHOW AS HTML: CLUSTER_SUMMARY.HTML”
- Then a demo page should open as in the following image:

Selected	Cluster ID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSD)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
false	0	110	0.841	2016	beta diversity; elevational gradient; secondary succession; functional diversity; natural regeneration land use; seed removal pattern; active restoration; intraspecific variation; spatial pattern	beta diversity (3355.33, 1.0E-4); elevational gradient (2078.18, 1.0E-4); secondary succession (1949.39, 1.0E-4); functional diversity (1357.59, 1.0E-4); north america (1287.73, 1.0E-4)	monitoring recovery (8.18); former amazonian mine
false	1	109	0.766	2010	north america; seed dispersal; invasive species; native range; emerald ash borer carabid beetle; evaluating seed; two-phase seed dispersal; dispersal effectiveness; invasive plant leucaena leucocephala	north america (1943.79, 1.0E-4); beta diversity (1610.46, 1.0E-4); emerald ash borer (1393.74, 1.0E-4); species distribution modelling (1262.34, 1.0E-4); native range (1189.87, 1.0E-4)	monitoring recovery (1.49); former amazonian mine
false	3	46	0.918	2013	ant-plant symbioses; southeast asia; new species; leaf-cutting ant; ultraconserved element secondary extinction; transmitted pseudoacardia bacteria; interaction specificity; hyperdiverse trans-wallacean lizard lineage; independent overwater colonization	ant-plant symbioses (839.45, 1.0E-4); southeast asia (772.41, 1.0E-4); recent radiation (547.13, 1.0E-4); fungus-farming ant genus sericonymymex mayr (547.13, 1.0E-4); host-symbiont coevolution (547.13, 1.0E-4)	heritability detection (0.4); complex morphologica
false	4	42	1	2019	biodiversity hotspot; landscape restoration potential; practice-led assessment; distance; fruit trait distance; pioneer trees structure seed dispersal; fruit trait; tropical deforested landscape; biodiversity hotspot	landscape restoration potential (40.51, 1.0E-4); practice-led assessment (40.51, 1.0E-4); biodiversity hotspot (40.51, 1.0E-4); tropical deforested landscape (20.14, 1.0E-4); distance (20.14, 1.0E-4)	beta diversity (0.02); elevational gradient (0.01)
false	5	36	0.847	2010	genetic structure; fungal symbiont; landscape genetics; fragmented landscape; symbiont performance mediterranean landscape; plant diversity pattern; secondary forest succession; soil seed bank structure; dung beetle activities	genetic structure (1689.76, 1.0E-4); fungal symbiont (865, 1.0E-4); landscape genetics (610.41, 1.0E-4); symbiont performance (470.69, 1.0E-4); variable interaction specificity (470.69, 1.0E-4)	top reptilian predator (0.24); interstate highway
false	6	34	0.96	2018	new insight; uce phylogenomics; social parasitism; crazy ant; historical biogeography anthropogenic disturbance; head anatomy; biological invasion; uncovering cryptic diversity; enigmatic ant genus overbeckia	uce phylogenomics (1108.35, 1.0E-4); crazy ant (903.36, 1.0E-4); historical biogeography (857.82, 1.0E-4); phylogenetic relationship (738.35, 1.0E-4); host preference (732.67, 1.0E-4)	large lupine beetle sitona gressorius (0.51); feed
false	8	18	1	2020	is altitude a surrogate for the spatial patterns and determinants of lentic zooplankton communities?	determinant (21.84, 1.0E-4); surrogate (21.84, 1.0E-4); altitude (21.84, 1.0E-4); spatial pattern (21.84, 1.0E-4); lentic zooplankton (21.84, 1.0E-4)	beta diversity (0.02); elevational gradient (0.01)
false	10	17	0.974	2010	ant-mediated seed dispersal; american ant community; predicting future coexistence; ant species diversity; community composition few ant species; many plant; asymmetric interdependence; non-myrmecochorous plant; mediterranean habitat	ant-mediated seed dispersal (286.96, 1.0E-4); predicting future coexistence (200.43, 1.0E-4); american ant community (200.43, 1.0E-4); community composition (171.67, 1.0E-4); ant species diversity (171.67, 1.0E-4)	beta diversity (0.02); elevational gradient (0.01)
false	11	16	1	2019	monitoring recovery of tree diversity during tropical forest restoration: lessons from long-term trajectories of natural regeneration	monitoring recovery (21.43, 1.0E-4); lesson (21.43, 1.0E-4); long-term trajectories (21.43, 1.0E-4); tropical forest restoration (7.52, 0.01); tree diversity (5.27, 0.05)	beta diversity (0.02); elevational gradient (0.01)
false	13	13	1	2019	restoration success in former amazonian mines is driven by soil amendment and forest proximity	former amazonian mine (23.02, 1.0E-4); restoration success (23.02, 1.0E-4); soil amendment (23.02, 1.0E-4); beta diversity (0.11, 1.0); elevational gradient (0.09, 1.0)	beta diversity (0.02); elevational gradient (0.01)
false	14	9	0.986	2012	insect societies; organismal perspective; genetic structure; native ant supercolonies; cooperation mean kinship future direction; ant ecology; social coercion; larval development; ant species	organismal perspective (224.55, 1.0E-4); insect societies (224.55, 1.0E-4); native ant supercolonies (211.27, 1.0E-4); cooperation mean kinship (198.03, 1.0E-4); false perception (184.8, 1.0E-4)	beta diversity (0.01); elevational gradient (0.01)

- It shows how many clusters were found, key tables and more information.
- To copy this table:
 - o CTRL + A (select all)
 - o CTRL + C (copy)
 - o CTRL + V (paste)

- After that, we go back to citespace for the last step, where we must use the small tab on the right side:

- First press "BURSTNESS".
- Then press "VIEW".
- Then it gives you the option to choose which "TOP" of bibliographies you want to consider, for example I used the TOP 50.
- OK
- In which you have to open a new tab that has to look like the following image:

Top 50 References with the Strongest Citation Bursts

References	Year	Strength	Begin	End	2013 - 2023
Kotze DJ, 2011, ZOOKEYS, V0, PP55, DOI 10.3897/zookeys.100.1523, DOI	2011	27.84	2013	2016	
Roura-Pascual N, 2011, P NATL ACAD SCI USA, V108, P220, DOI 10.1073/pnas.1011723108, DOI	2011	20.21	2013	2016	
[Anonymous], 2011, R LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2011	19.78	2013	2015	
[Anonymous], 2012, R LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2012	17.88	2013	2015	
Schupp EW, 2010, NEW PHYTOL, V188, P333, DOI 10.1111/j.1469-8137.2010.03402.x, DOI	2010	14.1	2013	2015	
Schleuning M, 2011, PLOS ONE, V6, P0, DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0027785, DOI	2011	12.64	2013	2016	
[Anonymous], 2010, R LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2010	12.23	2013	2014	
Eliith J, 2009, ANNU REV ECOL EVOL S, V40, P677, DOI 10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.110308.120159, DOI	2009	11.7	2013	2014	
Palmer TM, 2010, P NATL ACAD SCI USA, V107, P17234, DOI 10.1073/pnas.1006872107, DOI	2010	11.26	2013	2015	
Eliith J, 2011, DIVERS DISTRIB, V17, P43, DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2010.00725.x, DOI	2011	11.05	2013	2016	
Nowicki P, 2011, OECOLOGIA, V167, P657, DOI 10.1007/s00442-011-2025-x, DOI	2011	10.32	2013	2015	
Peakall R, 2012, BIOINFORMATICS, V28, P2537, DOI 10.1093/bioinformatics/bts460, DOI	2012	12.95	2014	2017	
Earl DA, 2012, CONSERV GENET RESOUR, V4, P359, DOI 10.1007/s12686-011-9548-7, DOI	2012	12.95	2014	2017	
Excoffier L, 2010, MOL ECOL RESOUR, V10, P564, DOI 10.1111/j.1755-0998.2010.02847.x, DOI	2010	12.11	2014	2015	
R Development Core Team, 2013, R LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2013	11.56	2014	2015	
Blaimer BB, 2012, MOL PHYLOGENET EVOL, V65, P421, DOI 10.1016/j.ympev.2012.06.028, DOI	2012	10.92	2014	2017	
R Core Team, 2014, R LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2014	23.5	2015	2017	
Tamura K, 2013, MOL BIOL EVOL, V30, P2725, DOI 10.1093/molbev/mst197, DOI	2013	15.01	2015	2018	
Lanfear R, 2012, MOL BIOL EVOL, V29, P1695, DOI 10.1093/molbev/mss020, DOI	2012	14.15	2015	2017	
Team R.C., 2014, LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2014	13.16	2015	2017	
Ward PS, 2015, SYST ENTOMOL, V40, P61, DOI 10.1111/syen.12090, DOI	2015	11.57	2015	2017	
Bates D, 2015, J STAT SOFTW, V67, P1, DOI 10.18637/jss.v067.i01, DOI	2015	33.41	2016	2020	
Tamme R, 2014, ECOLOGY, V95, P505, DOI 10.1890/13-1000.1, DOI	2014	26.96	2016	2019	
R Core Team, 2019, LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2019	17.44	2019	2019	
Norden N, 2015, P NATL ACAD SCI USA, V112, P8013, DOI 10.1073/pnas.1500403112, DOI	2015	11.01	2016	2020	
R Core Team, 2021, LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2021	19.69	2021	2019	
Stamatidakis A, 2014, BIOINFORMATICS, V30, P1312, DOI 10.1093/bioinformatics/btu033, DOI	2014	17.97	2017	2019	
Melo FPL, 2013, TRENDS ECOL EVOL, V28, P462, DOI 10.1016/j.tree.2013.01.001, DOI	2013	10.62	2017	2018	
Oksanen J., 2020, PACKAGE VEGAN TITLE, V0, P0	2020	18.99	2020	2020	
R Core Team, 2017, R LANG ENV STAT COMP, V0, P0	2017	15.61	2018	2020	
Haddad NM, 2015, SCI ADV, V1, P0, DOI 10.1126/sciadv.1500052, DOI	2015	15.61	2018	2020	
Bullock JM, 2017, J ECOL, V105, P6, DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.12666, DOI	2017	12.19	2018	2020	

- Then, select all the information with the mouse, then press CTRL + C to copy and then CTRL + V to paste.

Appendix 2 Results of mapping the literature with Citespace.

Appendix 2 Figure 1 Clusters for the extended set of the search Beetles AND_dispersal AND modelling

Appendix 2 Figure 1 continuation Time line of the clusters for the extended set of the search Beetles AND_dispersal AND modelling.

Appendix 2 Table 1 Clusters characterization for the extended set of the search Beetles AND_dispersal AND_modelling.

ClusterID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSI)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	301	0.859	2019	agricultural landscape; dung beetle; functional diversity; landscape structure; dung beetle diversity ecosystem service; fragmented landscape; species richness; negative effect; relative role	dung beetle (19418.29, 1.0E-4); agricultural landscape (17016.17, 1.0E-4); functional diversity (14320.23, 1.0E-4); dung beetle diversity (13795.64, 1.0E-4); dung beetle assemblage (9806.29, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (3.68); mountain (3.68); inco
1	272	0.847	2005	fragmented landscape; heterogeneous landscape; natterjack toad; case study; individual behavior landscape structure; habitat quality; metapopulation dynamics; spatial population structure; biological control	heterogeneous landscape (4644.58, 1.0E-4); natterjack toad (3654.71, 1.0E-4); diffusion model (2669.55, 1.0E-4); spatial ecology (2594.9, 1.0E-4); fragmented landscape (2592.18, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.54); mountain (0.54); inco
2	228	0.89	2015	molecular phylogeny; historical biogeography; net-winged beetle; evolutionary history; case study aegean archipelago; mediterranean centipede scolopendra cingulata; biogeographic diversification; new world; early miocene	molecular phylogeny (19120.92, 1.0E-4); historical biogeography (14929.5, 1.0E-4); net-winged beetle (14917.42, 1.0E-4); evolutionary history (11251.47, 1.0E-4); new species (6887.1, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (1.52); mountain (1.52); inco
3	182	0.902	2015	dispersal syndrome; range expansion; dispersal distance; eco-evolutionary dynamics; life history species-area relationship; spatiotemporal dynamics; salt-marsh specialist spider erigone longipalpis; growth rate; protist tetrahymena thermophila	dispersal syndrome (11763, 1.0E-4); range expansion (7445.28, 1.0E-4); eco-evolutionary dynamics (5141.84, 1.0E-4); dispersal distance (5118.98, 1.0E-4); eco-evolutionary feedback (4057.34, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.8); mountain (0.8); incorp
4	167	0.852	2008	species-area relationship; species richness; beta diversity; forest herb; island biogeography metapopulation modelling; area-wide pest management strategies evaluation; assemblage composition; mediterranean standing water; water beetle biodiversity	species-area relationship (10114.03, 1.0E-4); forest herb (6626.61, 1.0E-4); beta diversity (5550.52, 1.0E-4); nestedness component (5422.92, 1.0E-4); island biogeography (4565.2, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.91); mountain (0.91); inco
5	137	0.883	2009	carabid beetle; ground beetle; fragmented landscape; landscape genetics; carabid beetle assemblage hollow oak; urban wildlife corridors conduit; local biodiversity erosion; western france; spider assemblage	landscape genetics (4399.39, 1.0E-4); wood cricket (2793.07, 1.0E-4); urbanisation gradient (2726.17, 1.0E-4); carabid beetle assemblage (2723.14, 1.0E-4); nw spain (2179.18, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.48); mountain (0.48); inco
6	131	0.86	2015	emerald ash borer; invasive species; north america; biological control; population dynamics spatiotemporal dynamics; offspring quality; reduced genetic diversity; parental population; invasive grass	emerald ash borer (17791.64, 1.0E-4); invasive species (5543.16, 1.0E-4); human-mediated dispersal (2435.75, 1.0E-4); invasive alien species (2404.06, 1.0E-4); allee effect (2079.64, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.42); mountain (0.42); inco
7	127	0.931	2000	winter wheat; purple loosestrife; spatial dynamics; population dynamics; carabid beetle organic farming system; recent avian extinction; dynamic spatio-temporal response; transient prey patches; lowland neutral grassland	winter wheat (1641.74, 1.0E-4); purple loosestrife (1305.86, 1.0E-4); nontarget feeding (646.54, 1.0E-4); lythrum salicaria (646.54, 1.0E-4); aphid prey (635.4, 1.0E-4)	distribution dispersal (0.03); field margin habita
8	125	0.964	1996	genetic structure; gypsy moth; population ecology; gene flow; population structure testing hypotheses; pollen dispersal; contrasting evidence; complex species; restricted gene flow	high population viscosity (449.77, 1.0E-4); ant formica paralugubris (449.77, 1.0E-4); native fire ant population (436.54, 1.0E-4); molecular marker (436.54, 1.0E-4); hierarchical analysis (436.54, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); populational herita
9	117	0.904	2013	species distribution model; ecological niche model; using species distribution model; potential distribution; range dynamics species distribution modelling; ecological niche modelling; new	species distribution model (4395.12, 1.0E-4); ecological niche model (3756.35, 1.0E-4); using species distribution model (3743.76, 1.0E-4); range dynamics	coastal dune carabid (0.44); mountain (0.44); inco

				zealand; predicting response; existing biodiversity conservation strategies	(2282.06, 1.0E-4); invasive plant species (1994.93, 1.0E-4)	
10	114	0.937	2013	beetle outbreak; bark beetle; bark beetle outbreak; southern rocky mountain; tree mortality british columbia; ecosystem service; beetle population; nutrient cycling; boreal forest	beetle outbreak (10389.28, 1.0E-4); bark beetle (7220.32, 1.0E-4); southern rocky mountain (5451.81, 1.0E-4); bark beetle outbreak (4378.36, 1.0E-4); british columbia canada (3690.57, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.52); mountain (0.52); inco
11	105	0.927	2019	bark beetle; central europe; beetle outbreak; bark beetle infestation; bark beetle outbreak rocky mountain subalpine forest; ips typographus; rocky mountain forest; below-canopy temperature; ips sexdentatus	bark beetle (6379.84, 1.0E-4); central europe (4249.18, 1.0E-4); bark beetle infestation (2858.11, 1.0E-4); mountain forest (2772, 1.0E-4); czech republic (2071.62, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.35); mountain (0.35); inco
12	95	0.905	2016	saproxylic beetle; saproxylic insect; forest management; pitch canker; lucanus cervus case study; monochamus galloprovincialis; elater ferrugineus; retention forestry; saproxylic beetle diversity	saproxylic insect (7609.42, 1.0E-4); saproxylic beetle (3994.08, 1.0E-4); pitch canker (3863.65, 1.0E-4); forest management (3510.05, 1.0E-4); lucanus cervus (3017.74, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.42); mountain (0.42); inco
13	69	0.986	2002	seed dispersal; theoretical perspective; long-distance dispersal; spatial pattern; seed dispersal pattern seedling recruitment; forest fragmentation; genetic structure; rapid variation; prunus mahaleb	theoretical perspective (988.71, 1.0E-4); seed dispersal pattern (682.9, 1.0E-4); seed dispersal (599.56, 1.0E-4); central borneo (560.84, 1.0E-4); long-distance dispersal (532.1, 1.0E-4)	incorporating pattern (0.02); disperser behaviour
14	64	0.916	2014	agricultural landscape; biological control; natural enemies; landscape composition; ecosystem service multiple scale; landscape diversity; alfalfa field; landscape configuration; adjacent habitat	agricultural intensification (3346.52, 1.0E-4); natural enemies (2730.75, 1.0E-4); biological control (2398.65, 1.0E-4); agricultural landscape structure (1939.04, 1.0E-4); multiple scale (1837.85, 1.0E-4)	coastal dune carabid (0.42); mountain (0.42); inco
15	44	0.955	2019	island biogeography; oceanic island; species-area relationship; general dynamic model; vascular plant diversity case study; future potential distribution; italian reserve; conservation biogeography; tenebrionid beetle	vascular plant diversity (1361.43, 1.0E-4); island biogeography (1256.52, 1.0E-4); community assembly (1158.28, 1.0E-4); suitable habitat (1107.51, 1.0E-4); hawaiian archipelago (1082.19, 1.0E-4)	laboratory-reared asian longhorned beetle (0.13);
16	41	0.983	2004	great lakes region; landscape context; ips pini; bark beetle; population dynamics multiple spatial scale; case study; monophagous herbivore; negative dietary effect; colorado potato beetle egg	great lakes region (1444.97, 1.0E-4); ips pini (1027.41, 1.0E-4); sheetweb spider (464.02, 1.0E-4); landscape-level synthesis (451.82, 1.0E-4); host-parasitoid spatial ecology (451.82, 1.0E-4)	resource concentration hypothesis (0.02); migratio
17	34	1	1994	rangeland grasshopper; flightless defoliator; tussock moth; density-dependence test; chaotic dynamics coastal dune carabid; flightless defoliator; taylors power-law; chaotic dynamics; tussock moth	rangeland grasshopper (131.71, 1.0E-4); flightless defoliator (87.42, 1.0E-4); tussock moth (87.42, 1.0E-4); density-dependence test (65.44, 1.0E-4); taylors power-law (43.44, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);
19	27	0.992	2004	spatial synchrony; population dynamics; population synchrony; fluctuating population; lepidoptera species moran effect; parasitoid persistence; periodic local disturbance; host-parasitoid metapopulation; host suppression	spatial synchrony (1263.33, 1.0E-4); population synchrony (423.7, 1.0E-4); fluctuating population (365.08, 1.0E-4); larval phenology (321.25, 1.0E-4); north american oak (306.64, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);
20	25	0.999	2013	western corn rootworm; diabrotica virgifera virgifera; western corn rootworm population; feeding preference; field-evolved resistance mon863 transgenic maize root; western corn rootworm larvae; field cage; refuge maize; quantifying rate	western corn rootworm (1094, 1.0E-4); western corn rootworm population (403.77, 1.0E-4); feeding preference (313.86, 1.0E-4); inheritance fitness cost	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);

					(313.86, 1.0E-4); field-evolved resistance (298.77, 1.0E-4)	
22	21	0.984	2002	genetic consequence; iberian diving beetle; pleistocene refugia; parnassius smintheus; historic cycle habitat type; genetic population differentiation; female sexual receptivity; spontaneous abortion; iberian diving beetle	genetic consequence (251.61, 1.0E-4); using mitochondrial dna (217.88, 1.0E-4); historic cycle (217.88, 1.0E-4); modern biogeography (201.09, 1.0E-4); quaternary diversification (184.31, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);
23	16	0.988	2000	spatially-explicit model; remotely-sensed data; spatial effect; spatial distribution; desert-dwelling acacia spatial effect; desert-dwelling acacia; spatially-explicit model; long-term population dynamics; remotely-sensed data	remotely-sensed data (154.04, 1.0E-4); spatially-explicit model (102.07, 1.0E-4); spatial effect (43.44, 1.0E-4); desert-dwelling acacia (43.44, 1.0E-4); snapshot information (21.67, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);
24	11	0.989	2012	evolutionary theory; developmental biology; feeding plasticity; social context; developmental speed pristonchus pacificus; nematode model species; wide analysis; functional genomics; copy number variation	pristonchus pacificus (388.31, 1.0E-4); developmental biology (294.87, 1.0E-4); evolutionary theory (294.87, 1.0E-4); feeding plasticity (279.33, 1.0E-4); social context (279.33, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);
25	9	0.994	1993	displacement and aggregation of mountain pine beetles, dendroctonus-ponderosae (coleoptera, scolytidae), in response to their antiaggregation and aggregation pheromones	mountain (23.78, 1.0E-4); beetle (23.78, 1.0E-4); antiaggregation (23.78, 1.0E-4); aggregation (23.78, 1.0E-4); displacement (23.78, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);
26	8	1	1993	unthinned lodgepole; mountain pine-beetle; colonization pattern; stand; lodgepole lodgepole; forest; central oregon; bole-wood decomposition; unthinned lodgepole	unthinned lodgepole (46.03, 1.0E-4); mountain pine-beetle (46.03, 1.0E-4); stand (46.03, 1.0E-4); colonization pattern (27.54, 1.0E-4); lodgepole (22.92, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);
32	5	0.999	2006	western palaeartic parnassiinae; many species; mitochondrial dna divergence; geological history; phylogenetic analysis western north america; eastern asia; intercontinental disjunction; kelloggia torrey; phylogenetic information	mitochondrial dna divergence (162.46, 1.0E-4); western palaeartic parnassiinae (162.46, 1.0E-4); many species (162.46, 1.0E-4); angiosperm family araceae (144.25, 1.0E-4); multiple sequential invasion (144.25, 1.0E-4)	agricultural landscape (0.01); dung beetle (0.01);

Appendix 2 Figure 1 Clusters for the extended set of the search Amphibian AND dispersal AND_modelling

CiteSpace, v. 5.1.R6 (64-bit) Basic
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 WoS: D:\LITERATURA\X_AND_dispersal_AND_modelling\Amphibian_AND_dispersal_AND_modelling\DATE_FILTERATE
 Timespan: 2006-2023 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: Top 50 per slice, LRF=3.0, L/N=10, LBY=5, $\alpha=1.0$
 Network: N=627, E=2000 (Density=0.0153)
 Largest CC: 554 (88%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.7726
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.919
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.8461

Appendix 2 Figure 1 continuation Time line of the clusters for the extended set of the search Amphibian AND dispersal AND_modelling

Appendix 2 Table 1 Clusters characterization for the extended set of the search Amphibian AND dispersal AND_modelling.

ClusterID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSI)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	101	0.82	2017	case study; functional diversity; batrachochytrium dendrobatidis; landscape genetics; genetic structure ground beetle; amphibian conservation; species distribution; scale-dependent effect; natural history	new species (9635.83, 1.0E-4); functional diversity (7301.25, 1.0E-4); environmental driver (5321.48, 1.0E-4); potential distribution (5011.65, 1.0E-4); landscape genetics (4801.79, 1.0E-4)	songbird occurrence (5.92); chinese giant salamand
1	90	0.919	2008	landscape genetics; gene flow; genetic structure; genetic differentiation; landscape resistance landscape feature; genetic connectivity; genetic diversity; population structure; landscape connectivity	landscape genetics (28985.17, 1.0E-4); gene flow (12390.08, 1.0E-4); genetic structure (7619.79, 1.0E-4); genetic differentiation (6973.19, 1.0E-4); landscape resistance (6336.97, 1.0E-4)	songbird occurrence (2.09); chinese giant salamand
2	55	0.908	2015	new species; cryptic diversity; historical biogeography; integrative taxonomy; phylogenetic relationship phylogeographic pattern; north african water frog pelophylax saharicus; colletotrichum kahawae; colonization route; severe pathogen	new species (25390.98, 1.0E-4); cryptic diversity (8951.74, 1.0E-4); integrative taxonomy (6921.74, 1.0E-4); landscape genetics (6176.86, 1.0E-4); historical biogeography (5463.12, 1.0E-4)	songbird occurrence (1.53); chinese giant salamand
3	53	0.94	2004	marbled salamander; habitat selection; agricultural landscape; pond-breeding amphibian; gray treefrog central italy; amphibian decline; bornean stream frog; assemblage structure; species diversity	marbled salamander (3350.97, 1.0E-4); gray treefrog (2493.6, 1.0E-4); terrestrial habitat (1576.44, 1.0E-4); amphibian metacommunity (1534.02, 1.0E-4); wood frog rana sylvatica (1521.91, 1.0E-4)	songbird occurrence (0.46); chinese giant salamand
4	52	0.924	2005	species distribution; ensemble forecasting; case study; invasive species; conservation planning species distribution model; invasive bullfrog; water proxies; water availability; hybrid bayesian network classifier	species distribution (5448.24, 1.0E-4); ensemble forecasting (3082.27, 1.0E-4); suitable area (2050.62, 1.0E-4); stream fish assemblage (1721.46, 1.0E-4); plant species distribution (1514.06, 1.0E-4)	songbird occurrence (0.26); chinese giant salamand
5	49	0.992	2019	species distribution model; agricultural landscape; modelling potential natural pest control ecosystem service; future distribution; land use change chinese giant salamander; spatial transferability; natterjack toad; yellow-legged frog distribution; within-species niches	modelling potential natural pest control ecosystem service (211.63, 1.0E-4); triturus marmoratus (195.31, 1.0E-4); chinese fire-bellied newt (178.99, 1.0E-4); pond breeding amphibian (162.69, 1.0E-4); upward elevational shift (162.69, 1.0E-4)	landscape genetics (0.02); genetic structure (0.02)
6	45	0.866	2011	case study; atlantic forest; species trait; environmental change; species vulnerability protected area; species distribution model; batrachochytrium salamandrivoran; batrachochytrium dendrobatidis; land-use change	landscape genetics (3220.02, 1.0E-4); species trait (3070.05, 1.0E-4); protected area (2786.43, 1.0E-4); environmental change (2396.31, 1.0E-4); land use change (2067.49, 1.0E-4)	songbird occurrence (0.78); chinese giant salamand
7	34	0.999	2019	body size; malagasy skink; diversification rate; steady win; gene flow gene flow; sequence capture; afromontane forest; cameroon highland; endemic frog	steady win (112.79, 1.0E-4); malagasy skink (112.79, 1.0E-4); endemic greek stream frog rana (93.93, 1.0E-4); afromontane forest (75.01, 1.0E-4); endemic frog (75.01, 1.0E-4)	landscape genetics (0.02); genetic structure (0.02)

8	31	0.974	2006	historical biogeography; species richness; new species; middle american treefrog; phylogenetic relationship case study; biparental care; key ecological trait; pacific coast; inverse latitudinal gradient	middle american treefrog (1684.46, 1.0E-4); global pattern (1495.11, 1.0E-4); niche conservatism (1407.13, 1.0E-4); molecular phylogenetics (1152.59, 1.0E-4); species richness pattern (1100.43, 1.0E-4)	songbird occurrence (0.23); chinese giant salamand
9	26	1	2019	phylogeography and taxonomy of coleonyx elegans gray 1845 (squamata: eublepharidae) in mesoamerica: the isthmus of tehuantepec as an environmental barrier	taxonomy (23.42, 1.0E-4); environmental barrier (23.42, 1.0E-4); mesoamerica (23.42, 1.0E-4); isthmus (23.42, 1.0E-4); coleonyx elegans (23.42, 1.0E-4)	landscape genetics (0.03); genetic structure (0.02)
11	13	0.999	2002	habitat fragmentation; fragmented landscape; species responses; confounding factor; habitat connectivity co-occurring redhorse; river fragmentation; genetic consequence; species trait; contemporary driver	confounding factor (377.44, 1.0E-4); agri-environment scheme (364.41, 1.0E-4); matrix restoration (364.41, 1.0E-4); reversing habitat loss (351.38, 1.0E-4); larch plantation matrix (351.38, 1.0E-4)	landscape genetics (0.02); genetic structure (0.01)
12	5	1	2018	chaos does not drive lower synchrony for intrinsically-induced population fluctuations	chao (25.34, 1.0E-4); synchrony (25.34, 1.0E-4); intrinsically-induced population fluctuation (25.34, 1.0E-4); landscape genetics (0.12, 1.0); case study (0.12, 1.0)	landscape genetics (0.03); genetic structure (0.02)

Appendix 2 Figure 1 Clusters for the extended set of the search Reptile AND_dispersal AND modelling.

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 WoS: D:\LITERATURA\X_AND_dispersal_AND_modelling\Reptile_AND_dispersal_AND_modelling\DATE_FILTERATE
 Timespan: 2010-2023 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: Top 50 per slice, LRF=3.0, L/N=10, LBY=5, q=1.0
 Network: N=512, E=2463 (Density=0.0188)
 Largest CC: 450 (87%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.7071
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.9137
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.7972

Appendix 2 Figure 1 continuation Time line of the clusters for the extended set of the search Reptile AND_dispersal AND modelling.

Appendix 2 Table 1 Clusters characterization for the extended set of the search Reptile AND_dispersal AND modelling.

ClusterID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSI)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	82	0.938	2010	new species; molecular phylogeny; evolutionary history; cryptic diversity; socotra archipelago integrative taxonomy; phylogenetic placement; hemidactylus brookii; new genus; ecological niche	molecular phylogeny (1207.65, 1.0E-4); single radiation (1010.86, 1.0E-4); mediterranean basin (969.14, 1.0E-4); assessing species boundaries (909.57, 1.0E-4); african origin (909.57, 1.0E-4)	basin ne brazil (2.23); ryukyu archipelago (2.23);
1	79	0.943	2007	species distribution; suitable area; ensemble forecasting; conservation planning; species distribution modelling case study; conservation strategies; semi-mechanistic community-level modelling; eucalyptus fastigata; landscape predictor	species distribution (1462, 1.0E-4); suitable area (1295.02, 1.0E-4); ensemble forecasting (902.7, 1.0E-4); conservation planning (720.39, 1.0E-4); ensemble forecasting shift (497.88, 1.0E-4)	basin ne brazil (0.27); ryukyu archipelago (0.27);
2	73	0.863	2017	habitat suitability; ecological niche model; evolutionary history; spatial population genomics; brown rat gene flow; thermal tolerance; tropical lizard; thermal ecology; intraspecific variation	new species (3500.15, 1.0E-4); cryptic diversity (1186.89, 1.0E-4); thermal tolerance (1103.99, 1.0E-4); tropical lizard (1083.79, 1.0E-4); thermal ecology (977.19, 1.0E-4)	basin ne brazil (4.21); ryukyu archipelago (4.21);
3	65	0.878	2016	new species; cryptic diversity; bent-toed gecko; hidden diversity; eastern myanmar ancient dna; hemidactylus gecko; southwestern arabia; endemic species; coastal plain	new species (3046.61, 1.0E-4); hidden diversity (1915.24, 1.0E-4); eastern myanmar (1696.19, 1.0E-4); bent-toed gecko (1497.23, 1.0E-4); cyrtodactylus gray (1096.43, 1.0E-4)	basin ne brazil (1.86); ryukyu archipelago (1.86);
4	54	0.843	2011	protected area; case study; global warming; potential effect; land use change population dynamics; private garden; public green space; ornamental plant species; freshwater biodiversity	species responses (1058.43, 1.0E-4); potential effect (765.18, 1.0E-4); protected area (617.95, 1.0E-4); new species (599.84, 1.0E-4); past rate (577.37, 1.0E-4)	basin ne brazil (1); ryukyu archipelago (1); regio
5	35	0.997	2019	body size; diversification rate; malagasy skink; steady win; southern europe giant earthworm; biogeographical history; metaphire formosae species group; ryukyu archipelago; new species	steady win (143.78, 1.0E-4); diversification rate (143.78, 1.0E-4); body size (143.78, 1.0E-4); malagasy skink (143.78, 1.0E-4); southern europe (129.35, 1.0E-4)	new species (0.01); evolutionary history (0.01); c
6	24	0.912	2016	biological invasion; economic cost; invasive alien species; alien species; global economic cost plant invasion; alien plant; geographic distribution; phylogenetic pattern; naturalized alien flora	biological invasion (1951.31, 1.0E-4); economic cost (1397.76, 1.0E-4); invasive alien species (610.85, 1.0E-4); alien species (607.6, 1.0E-4); global economic cost (531.47, 1.0E-4)	regional inventories (0.1); invasive alien plant (
7	20	0.975	2009	plant invasion; biological invasion; invasive species; global trade; weed risk assessment czech republic; invasion pattern; alien flora; checklist update; alien plant	plant invasion (1233, 1.0E-4); czech republic (750.59, 1.0E-4); invasion pattern (542.97, 1.0E-4); global trade (482.49, 1.0E-4); taxonomic diversity (387.53, 1.0E-4)	of plant invasion (0.09); taxonomic challenges for
8	7	1	2013	liberating levy walk research; foraging pattern; online searches; st mark; albatross levy flight fractal analysis; new insight; surfacing pattern; marine mammal welfare assessment; marine mammal behavior	liberating levy walk research (585.19, 1.0E-4); online searches (232.44, 1.0E-4); foraging pattern (232.44, 1.0E-4); st mark (206.52, 1.0E-4); albatross levy flight (206.52, 1.0E-4)	new species (0.01); swarm dynamics (0.01); basin n

9	6	0.998	2006	pathogenic chytrid fungus; panamanian golden frog; hydric environment; threatened terrestrial vertebrate; central spain central italy; protected area; human-provoked amphibian decline; central spain; threatened terrestrial vertebrate	hydric environment (102.16, 1.0E-4); panamanian golden frog (102.16, 1.0E-4); pathogenic chytrid fungus (102.16, 1.0E-4); central spain (86.48, 1.0E-4); threatened terrestrial vertebrate (86.48, 1.0E-4)	new species (0.02); evolutionary history (0.01); c
10	5	0.986	2015	evolution preface; mesozoic marine reptile; diving adaptation; hematological convergence; extant aquatic amniote endocranial anatomy; west antarctica; elasmosaurid pelvic girdle; morphological diversity; upper cretaceous	evolution preface (261.21, 1.0E-4); extant aquatic amniote (249.83, 1.0E-4); diving adaptation (249.83, 1.0E-4); mesozoic marine reptile (249.83, 1.0E-4); hematological convergence (249.83, 1.0E-4)	basin ne brazil (0.02); south atlantic (0.02); ear